

Bilingual Argumentative Discourse Unit Detection for Argument Mining on French and German Proceedings of the European Parliament

Master Thesis

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Abstract

Argumentation Mining aims at automatically extracting structured arguments from unstructured textual documents [54]. This work addresses the conduction of a cross-lingual argumentation mining task, the detection of argumentative discourse units (ADU)s. Our contribution is two-fold: firstly, we extract a German and French ADU-annotated parallel corpus for further research, secondly, we thereupon compare five state-of-the-art language models (LM)s. Following the CRISP-DM framework for data mining [13], we prepare the data from the popular Europarl corpus by conducting a topic modeling to semantically trim corpus size. On the French and German subcorpus, annotations are made, distinguishing between the labels “*non-argumentative*”, “*claim*” and “*premise*”. Given the human baseline, in the modeling phase, the five LMs German BERT, German DistilBERT, CamemBERT, mBERT and mDistilBERT are compared on the sentence classification task. The task is performed by the LMs with moderate success. There is a performance difference between German and French models, leading to the insight that considering the input language as a feature and not only a parameter is crucial. Other than that, the beneficial influence of multilingual pretraining is discussed, triggering a need for further research.

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List of Abbreviations

ADU Argumentative Discourse Unit

AM Argument Mining

AZ Argumentative Zoning

BERT Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers

BoW Bag of Words

CEFR Common European Framework for Reference of Language

CNN Convolutional Neural Network

CSV Comma-Separated Values

ECHR European Court of Human Rights

ELMo Embeddings from Language Models

EU European Union

FFNN Feedforward Neural Network

GUI Graphical User Interface

HTML Hypertext Markup Language

IAA Inter-Annotator Agreement

KC Knowledge Claim

LDA Latent Dirichlet Allocation

LM Language Model

LtR Left-to-Right

LSTM Long Short-Term Memory

LRE Language Resources and Evaluation

MCC Matthews Correlation Coefficient

ML Machine Learning

MLM Masked Language Modeling

NER Named-Entity Recognition

NLI Natural Language Inference

NLP Natural Language Processing

NLTK Natural Language Toolkit

NLU Natural Language Understanding

NN Neural Network

NSP Next Sentence Prediction

PoS Part of Speech

RNN Recurrent Neural Network

ROC Receiver Operating Characteristic

RtL Right-to-Left

SMT Statistical Machine Translation

SVM Support Vector Machines

ULMFiT Universal Language Model Fine-Tuning

UML Unified Modeling Language

UTF-8 Universal Transformation Format-8

WALS World Atlas of Language Structures

XML eXtensible Markup Language

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1. Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Argumentation forms the basis of human thought processes and communication. For some professional fields, such as journalism, legal practice, politics or medicine, argumentation plays an even more crucial role. Thus, computationally assisted systems, so-called argumentation machines or argument mining (AM) systems, have the goal to support and accelerate the information retrieval for argumentative data supplying these fields [4].

As the need for data to build AM systems is massive, research focuses disproportionately on the English language, enforcing the English role as a high-resource language, eventually leading to a dangerous language divide. This development is harmful due to the lacking representativeness of English, the ignorance of different linguistic markets, and the risk of depreciation through the rise of transfer learning.

First and foremost, the English language is not representative of all human languages. There is an estimation of 7117 languages spoken in the world [22]. According to the number of speakers, English ranks third having 370 million speakers after Mandarin and Spanish, with 921 million and 463 million speakers respectively [22]. On the contrary, the Language Resources and Evaluation (LRE) Map in 2019 contains 1082 English datasets, followed by other European languages with approximately a fifth, the remainder providing even fewer resources [10]. Despite its dominant role, most languages do not share the same morphological typology, meaning word composition, and language family, meaning geographical origin, as English. Due to these divergences, Natural Language Processing (NLP) systems using n -grams, tokens composed of n subsequent words, do not deliver stable results when handed new input languages, because word order follows different rules depending on the grammar-giving language. Hence, what is said to be Natural Language Processing, turns out to be English Processing if expressed concisely [2].

Secondly, from an economical perspective, it is irrational to ignore application areas outside of the English-speaking world. The use of an argumentation machine in multilingual scenarios is obvious. On a large scale, scenarios such as debate analysis on an international level are conceivable, where a journalist or political scientist analyses arguments in real-time, an idea partially realized in [5]. There is a significant amount of argumentative content that requires cooperation on an international level, such as climate crisis, poverty or pandemic protection. Points of administration could be governments, parliaments, or international news and social media analysis. This is just one application scenario out of many. On a small scale, small and medium-sized enterprises could profit even more from decision support through multilingual argumentation machines. As data is only available in the respective source language, many application fields suffer from the language divide. If a French doctor needs ma-

chine decision support on whether or not to administer a risky medication, his local patient data is encoded in French. If a lawyer in Germany has to collect arguments for or against a tax increase, his knowledge base is encoded in German. Machine Translation is costly and often not applicable through the usage of technical jargon, which is wide-spread in domains of knowledge work. To summarize these thoughts, the language of an argumentation machine matters, both to aggregate international discussions and to help coping with present, language-dependent data ubiquitous in local enterprises.

So far, the major reason behind the research focus on the English language is constrained by the huge amount of training data and computation costs necessary for supervised Machine Learning. There is only a limited number of annotated corpora available as the creation of a sufficient amount of training data is monetary and time expensive as it requires manual work and domain expertise, triggering a network effect that leads to exclusion of other language communities [56]. Yet, in recent years this constraint is not holding any longer. With the advances of self-attention-based language models (LM)s pretrained on semi-supervised learning tasks, effective prediction of language structures has become universally applicable[20]. These models are trained on vast amounts of linguistic data, some of which are encoded in miscellaneous languages, even allowing an application on multilingual tasks [70], with only a minor tuning effort. This development could serve as a door opener for multilingual AM systems.

To oppose the language divide, this work will explore the first step in the AM process, Argumentative Discourse Unit (ADU) detection on two languages other than English. Following the CRISP-DM standard for Data Mining procedures [13], a German and French dataset extracted from the Europarl Parallel Corpus [50] will be distilled, sampled, annotated and used as input data for some state-of-the-art LMs to be systematically assessed upon. Thus, the thesis delivers a first measurement of the feasibility and potentials of Argumentation Machines based on languages other than English. As the data are preprocessed and tailored from scratch to the ADU detection task, aspects peculiar to the bilingual origin of the data are to be emphasized. Thereupon, a focus lies on the identification of difficulties along the ADU detection pipeline when dealing with multiple languages to guarantee a systematic experimental process. These considerations in mind, the area of tension spanned between language and argumentation holds some open challenges, waiting to be investigated.

1.2 Research Objective

Current approaches of argumentation machines are tackling the issue as if there were only one language. Although there already are solutions facing AM by the means of Transfer Learning [100], the potentials of multilingual applications are still unused. To address these shortcomings, this thesis exemplarily examines the German and French languages in the domain of detection of arguments in textual data, scrutinizing possible sources of influence deviating from the English language. To realize this endeavor while remaining within the scope of a master's thesis, some simplifying assumptions have to be set.

The first assumption determines the scope of the AM task. To avoid boundary detection issues, the task is designed as a simple sentence classification. Furthermore, the languages of scrutiny are twofold: French and German. The more languages are

scrutinized, the more versatile is the data basis, yet two languages should suit the needs of an exploratory study. The languages are chosen due to prior knowledge and comparable language community sizes. The choice of two languages instead of one, should raise awareness of modeling differences during implementation and as such create a baseline. Logically following of the languages, a suitable data basis and classifiers for the ADU detection task have to be identified. As they are both commonly used, LMs from the Hugging Face library [102] will be fed with data extracted from the Europarl corpus, a corpus containing the proceedings of the European parliament in different languages.

To summarize, this thesis aims to assess German and French LMs on a newly extracted corpus specified for the detection of ADUs at sentence level. This broader research objective leads to three specific research hypotheses to be evaluated in this work.

- **H1: There is a performance difference between German and French LMs.**
If there is an identifiable difference between the LMs pretrained in different languages, there is a reason to suspect that the input language influences the ADU detection quality and therefore it is useful to include the factor "language" when building an argumentation machine.
- **H2: There is a performance difference between monolingually and multilingually pretrained LMs.**
On one hand, some LMs are fine-tuned to only one language, to lead to stronger performance in Natural Language Understanding (NLU) tasks in the respective language. On the other hand, the volume of training data is assumed to have a positive effect on LM performance. How these two tendencies are influencing each other is to be explored.
- **H3: German and French LMs perform worse than English LMs from the literature.**
This hypothesis aims to verify the assumed negative influence of the research language divide in NLP on the AM domain. Should H3 and H1 be confirmed in the experiments, further experiments on linguistic implications for AM could be justified.

Moreover, the identified research objective has to be aligned with the conceptualization of the experiments. Therefore, it is of utter importance that the methodology is clearly outlined and documented in order to generate comparability, that choices are made as agnostically as possible when preprocessing the bilingual data to enable a clear identification of parallels and differences in the workflows.

1.3 Structure of Work

The remainder of the thesis is structured as follows. Overall, the thesis comprises six major chapters: "*introduction*", "*background*", "*method*", "*evaluation*", "*discussion and outlook*", and "*conclusion*"; each again subdivided into several sections. The first chapter, "*introduction*" 1, outlines the reasons behind this work 1.1, defines the research objective 1.2 and hereby gives a structural overview of the thesis 1.3. Chapter 2 lays the theoretical background, where the subsequent practical realization builds on. The theoretical part of the thesis is subdivided into four sections. Section 2.1 starts non-technical, explaining the linguistic foundations of this work, further collecting information on the thought expressed in the motivation that the composition of a language might influence its computational processing. Afterward, section 2.2 deals with the foundations of AM, showing how arguments are built according to different models with the claim-premise model as the common ground. Other than that, an eye will be kept on the structure of argumentation in different disciplines, ending with argumentation in computer science. Then, the technical foundations of this work are presented in the shape of the transformer 2.3. After giving a short introduction to the recent developments in NLP, the architecture behind the LMs to be scrutinized will be explained at a high level, including the workings of the input data, their preparation mechanism for the classifier, as well as the classifier itself. In the final background section, the contribution of the thesis will be worked out, in contrast to previous work 2.4.

Chapter 3, "*method*", contains the practical realization of the ADU detection experiment based on the vocabulary elaborated in the previous chapter. As the method is the body of this thesis, it comprises the largest volume. The method is aligned to the CRISP-DM framework, further revised in section 3.1. As the foundations corresponding to the business understanding phase are covered in chapter 2, section 3.2 deals with the data understanding phase by giving detailed insights to the Europarl corpus. Sections 3.3, 3.4 and 3.5 all cover the data preparation. As such, section 3.3 describes how the data volume of the corpus was trimmed using the topic structure of Europarl. In section 3.4, the ADU annotation of the trimmed corpus is described, including the annotation process, the used annotation scheme derived from the knowledge of section 2.2.1, annotation guidelines, lessons learned, and the analysis of Inter-Annotator agreement (IAA) to guarantee annotation reproducibility and stability. The annotated corpus is then further preprocessed to fit the LMs expected input format in section 3.5 so that in sections 3.6 and 3.7 the learning phase will be portrayed. The learning or modeling phase defines the ADU detection experiments, further containing the selection of LMs, the hardware environment, implementation and parametrization as well as fine-tuning steps to achieve the best possible results. The experiments' findings will subsequently be evaluated in chapter 4, which will be later discussed and put into context in chapter 5. The last chapter 6 gives a summarizing conclusion of the findings.

2. Background

To set up the elementary foundations and concepts that this thesis will elaborate on, chapter 2 describes some background knowledge. The chapter is arranged by the interdisciplinary area of tension, in which the scope of this thesis lies. Thus, subsequently the "*why*", "*what*" and "*how*" of bilingual ADU detection are the topic of scrutiny. The first section covers the linguistic foundations, such as: why does measuring languages matter for an NLP task? What are the basic differences between the French and the German language from an objective point of view? How do parallel corpora deal with these differences? This first section should give a first insight into the factors which should be considered when handling multilingual data and thereby contribute to the motivational aspect of this work. In section two, the focus is shifted to the "*what*", or to state more precisely, the Argument Mining tasks themselves, of which the ADU detection incorporates the first step. The structure of arguments and their smallest atomic units, the ADUs are introduced in a narrow scope. Then, in a broader scope, argumentation patterns in different disciplines are highlighted, finishing by the processing of argumentation patterns in computer science, the AM pipeline.

The means of the presented ADU detection, the "*how*", is oriented by the state of the art in NLP, namely the utilization of recent LMs profiting from a semi-supervised pretraining on large amounts of mono- and multilingual data, an approach based on the idea of transfer learning. The architectures exploited for this work are based on transfer learning, the loading of pretrained weights inspired by human transfer learning. The data structure used, the transformer, needs a special embedding of the positional signal, distinguishing it from the historically used Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN)s. Further, the concept of attention is introduced, followed by an overview of FFNNs and how they learn. After the technological background is set, the reader has all the knowledge to understand the models implemented in related work.

2.1 Linguistic Background

2.1.1 Measuring Languages

The research focus on NLP tasks based on English corpora leads to a language divide with an increasing number of insights gained for the English language and a declining number of insights for other languages [46]. Instead, the current language divide should be replaced by language independence, a concept in which NLP applications deliver sound results, independently of their input language. As there is a gap between intended and existing situation, papers in NLP should at minimum document the languages they are working with following the Bender-rule [2].

To achieve language independence, one first has to be aware of internal and external variances between languages. One has to measure language. However, this task is challenging in two ways. On one hand, language is fuzzy in nature. It is not as complete as mathematical definitions or as observable as biological phenomena. For instance, it is difficult to assign the term “*warm*” to an exact temperature. On the other hand, language is human-made and constantly evolving. Hence, linguistic structures cannot easily be predefined, since they emerge by comparison with other linguistic structures. The field of linguistic typology thus has set itself the goal to systematically document and compare the world’s languages based on the empirical observation of their variation with respect to cross-lingual benchmarks [71]. The units of documentation, chosen in linguistic typology are typological features. Typological features are formalized as attribute-value pairs, built out of construction and strategy. The construction is an abstract construct, appearing across various languages as for instance “*number of genders*”. The strategy is the corresponding way in which the construction is implemented in a specific language. For instance, the number of genders in German is three (“*der*”, “*die*”, “*das*”), in French is two (“*le*”, “*la*”) and in English is one (“*the*”). Figure 2.1 illustrates the feature allocation of genders as found in the World Atlas of Language Structures Online (WALS), a database collecting over 192 features in 2679 languages [57]

Figure 2.1: Typological feature “*number of genders*” in WALS [57].

Further, cross-lingual variations do not occur at random. There are regularities, which cross-lingual variations follow [33]. For instance, typological features possess implications and frequency. Some typological features are dependent on each other. An example are distributive numerals in Japanese, where suffixes are attached to the numeral according to the kind of object that is counted. This feature requires that numerals (words representing numbers) occur in the language of scrutiny. Surprisingly, the concept of numerals is not ubiquitous in all languages, as for example in Pirahã, a language spoken in the Amazon region, there are no numerals at all. The speakers only divide entities into large or small [25]. Such dependencies are described by the term “*restricted universal*” as opposed to the “*unrestricted universal*”, a feature holding independently across all languages. However, these regularities are

not designed, they evolve naturally. As every regularity comes with its exceptions, universals are measured statistically. Overall, typological features are not equally distributed. Some occur very often whereas others do not. Some features are more prevalent in one language family. Consider the word order within sentences in Romance languages, comprised by subject, verb and object. These frequent features lead to faster learning results when previous knowledge is already accumulated [71]. The origin of units and rules in linguistic typology can be interpreted by different approaches. Here, typologists distinguish between functional theories and event-based theories. Functional theories take the internal perspective on the creation of typological features. Furthermore, within functional theories, structural typology and sematic typology may be discerned. Structural typology is the study of elements and their combination. Variations between languages manifest themselves across all linguistic levels, e.g. through morphology, meaning parts of words and how they are built, or the formation of word order. In agglomerative languages, such as Turkish, grammatical functions are represented by a long concatenation of affixes. In inflected languages, such as German or French, exactly one affix is positioned at the end of the word to determine its grammatical role. Alternatively, semantic typology measures typological features by the concepts they are representing [30]. Semantic lexical classes and their representatives differ across languages. For instance, a Scottish thesaurus was found to contain more than 400 words for snow, even surpassing the Inuit languages [14]. Australian aborigines do not express directions as “*left*” and “*right*” according to the speaker, but instead in “*north*”, “*east*”, “*south*” and “*west*” according to the sun’s movement [40]. These variations are quite revealing as they show that how one language encodes a concept is no objective truth and that there are other systems with evenly matched mindsets.

Event-based theories take the external perspective, not searching for the origin of typological features in the components of a language, but in the influences of other languages [30]. As variations are historically grown and shared throughout language communities, there are two major pathways of influence. The first option is to share a common ancestry. As such, the two Germanic languages Afrikaans and English share the common ancestor Proto-Germanic and therefore share some typological features. The second option is that languages share typological features due to areal proximity such as the Baltic languages.

Both event-based and functional theories can be drawn upon to explain typological features. Nevertheless, they are not without intersection. As can be seen, linguistic typology delivers a systematic overview of the measurement of languages. In the next section, the features are applied to the languages of interest: French and German.

2.1.2 French and German

In the previous subchapter, linguistic typology as a way to measure language was presented. The languages serving as a base for this work are German and French due to existing prior knowledge. German is one of the Germanic languages, it comprises approximately 75.5 million speakers, mostly located in Germany, Austria and Switzerland [37]. French is a Gallo-Romance language with 77.3 million speakers predominantly in France, the Antilles and Switzerland [38]. In the following, a short grammatical overview of the similarities and differences is given to grasp their suitability for NLP tasks.

The Indo-European languages are split after their ancestors into the Romance, Germanic and the Baltic-Slavic. Although heterogeneous at first glance, these languages share some common typological features that distinguish them from languages spoken all over the world. Haspelmath [39] summarizes these features in a linguistic area called Standard Average European, at the core of which lie French and German. The linguistic area is defined by nine typological features found in both languages at hand: "definite and indefinite articles", "relative clauses with relative pronouns", "have-perfect", "participial passive", "dative external possessors", "negative pronouns and lack of verbal negation", "relative-based equative constructions", "subject person affixes as strict agreement markers" and "intensifier-reflexive differentiation".

In French and German, indefinite articles can be found (e.g. "un", "une", "ein", "eine"), indicating an affiliation to a category as for instance "I see a dog". Definite articles show the affiliation to a concrete entity of the category (e.g. "der", "die", "das", "le", "la") "I see the dog". This distinction between the concrete and the abstract affiliation to a class can only be found in one-third of the world languages [39]. Both languages have a relative pronoun strategy, meaning that relative clauses are introduced by an inflecting relative pronoun, which is often interrogative (e.g. "the woman, who went over the street", "die Frau, welche die Straße überquerte", "la dame qui a traversé la rue"). Other prominent features are the usage of a past perfect tense, built with "to have" and a past participle (e.g. "I have bought", "ich habe gekauft", "j'ai acheté") and a participial passive voice, built with "to be" and a passive participle (e.g. "he is hit", "er ist geschlagen", "il est frappé"). Additionally, external possessor structures are found in French and German but not in English. These structures are clauses, in which the possessor of an entity is fixed through the usage of a dative such as "die Mutter gibt dem Kind ein Geschenk" or „la mère donne un cadeau au fils“. The feature "negative pronouns and lack of verbal negation" describes a form of negation through pronouns (e.g. "nobody comes to the party", "niemand kommt zu der Party", "personne ne vient à la fête"). Further, relative-based equative constructions follow the structure "smaller than X". There is a comparison particle such as "than", "als" or "que" and the noun before the comparison is not inflected. Hence, there is a difference between "I love you more than her" and "I love you more than she". Adverbial relative clause equative constructions between equal entities exist in German and French, such as "stark wie ein Löwe" and "aussi fort qu'un lion". The feature "subject person affixes" captures the inflection of a word based on its grammatical person. Possible strategies are "referential", meaning, the affix uniquely determines the grammatical person or "strict", meaning, the affix only determines a set of grammatical persons. For instance, in German, the affix "-et" in "arbeitet" could belong to a third person singular "sie arbeitet" or a second person plural "ihr arbeitet" and is therefore not uniquely assigned. In many languages, intensifiers such as "the king himself came to the parade" and reflexive pronouns "he gave himself a high-five" are expressed by the exact same words (here: "himself"). In German and French, intensifiers and reflexive pronouns are differentiated. In German, the intensifier is "selbst" and the reflexive pronoun "sich". Likewise, in French the intensifier is "même" and the reflexive pronoun "se". On the contrary to the similarities resulting from their areal proximity, German and French also vary in several features [57]. In the similar feature "subject person affixes", French and German only show a strict agreement, meaning the suffix of a verb does not uniquely describe its grammatical person. The universal inflectional synthesis builds on this feature by further assessing the granularity of conjugations.

Hence, in French, verb forms vary between four to five categories per word whereas in German there are only two to three. For instance, the French language comprises an inflected future tense “*je volera*” while German uses auxiliary verbs to express the future “*ich werde fliegen*”. A further difference is the presence of cases in German. Depending on a noun’s quantity, gender, function in a sentence (“*who?*”, “*whom?*”) and presence of an ownership relation (“*of whom?*”), a different suffix is added, a conception that is not existing in French. Meanwhile in French, features regarding word order are very prominent, which cannot be found in German. The complementarity of these features is again a nice example of related concepts that are expressed differently. Table 2.1 shows a collection of differentiating features of German and French in the WALS database.

WALS-ID	Feature	Value-FR	Value-DE	Area
22A	Inflectional Synthesis of the Verb	4-5 categories per word	2-3 categories per word	Morphology
30A	Number of genders	2 genders	3 genders	Nominal categories
49A	Number of cases	No morphological case-marking	4 cases	Nominal categories
67A	The future tense	Inflectional future exists	No inflectional future	Verbal categories
81A	Order of Subject, Object and Verb	SVO	No dominant order	Word order
87A	Order of Adjective and Noun	Noun-adjective	Adjective-noun	Word order
92A	Position of Polar Question Particles	Initial	No question particle	Word order

Table 2.1: Deviating strategies in French and German following [57].

The above presented features of French and German have practical implications on NLP-tasks working with them. For example, in German, a significant amount of information is attached to suffixes of nouns. Therefore, caution is given when preprocessing the data with a stemmer. Similar is the case of the highly-inflected French verbs. In French, word order is rather strict and plays an important role. Due to this, n-grams and Part-of-Speech(PoS) tags should be considered in the feature selection. It should be kept in mind that words in different languages are attached by a different glue and that decisions should be made in an informed manner. The next subchapter will finish the linguistic background by pointing out how large corpora are dealing with multilingualism.

2.1.3 Parallel Corpora

The earliest predecessor of modern parallel corpora is the Rosetta Stone 200 BC. The ancient stone tablet has text written on it in three languages, handing the translator Champollion the key to decode Egyptian hieroglyphs in the 19th century. Today, large parallel corpora are collections of texts in multiple languages aligned by topic, genre and period [79]. The corpora are frequently used as training and test resources for statistical machine translation (SMT), analysis of lexical frequency and collocations and many more NLP-tasks. The analysis' outputs are statistically reliable due to the massive size of these corpora. Most commonly used corpora are collected from public institutions and governments of multilingual countries such as Canada [31]. As these sources are naturally limited, corpora vary in their degree of comparability.

Fully parallel. Examples for the full parallel corpus are the UN collection of documents [104], and Europarl [50], which is further covered in chapter 3.2. A parallel corpus contains document-, paragraph- or sentence-aligned data that was accurately translated, except for minor differences, such as the replacement of proper names.

Strongly comparable. This category of corpora contains translations that are still alignable but already further edited. They can include the coverage of the same story, event or topic in different languages, parallel versions of the same article from different languages' Wikipedias or newsfeeds published in different languages.

Weakly comparable. Weakly comparable corpora incorporate even fewer restrictions, containing texts in multiple languages collected from a specified genre or domain. This includes varying subdomains such as crawled political forums in language A and language B. with different discussions.

Unrelated texts. Although no real category of comparable corpora, even unrelated data in different languages provide insights for linguistic analysis and learners.

Having seen the systematics behind languages, how they apply to German and French and how parallel corpora structure and digitize them, the subsequent background section will deal with persuasive language, argumentation.

2.2 Argument Mining

2.2.1 Architecture of Arguments

The following section presents the theory about the task of this thesis. It starts by setting the foundational knowledge on arguments as the fabric of argumentation, then moves to argumentation across different disciplines and finally treats argumentation in computer science illustrated by the AM pipeline.

Interestingly, the terms “*Argumentation Mining*” (AM) and “*Argument Mining*” are interchangeably used, although one appears to focus on a high-level pattern (argumentation) and one on a low-level pattern (as arguments are a mere tool in argumentation). As this thesis covers the detection of argumentative discourse units (ADU), in accordance with elementary discourse units from discourse theory, the representational perspective of arguments seems noteworthy in the context. Arguments are well-researched rhetorical devices since antiquity. They are a piece of speech suited to show the validity or invalidity of a thesis, which can be either described as a product or process [60].

Claim-Premise model. In its simplest form, an argument can be perceived as a product, arising from the crossover between premises and a conclusion [43]. A claim is a “*conclusion we seek to establish by our arguments*” [27]. For instance, a claim in the domain of public health could be: “*people should get vaccinated*”. The claim is the heart of the argument. Therefore, a well-formed argument should have exactly one claim. It has a clear stance for or against a persuasive thesis. In order to distinguish a claim from a non-argumentative opinion, it has to be accompanied by at least one premise, also called “*evidence*” or “*justification*”. Premises are “*evidence or reasoning advanced to establish the foundation of a claim*” [27]. In the afore-mentioned health example, a matching premise could be: “*vaccination helps a population to achieve herd immunity*”. A premise can either support or attack its claim. In monological argumentation, attacking premises are often used to introduce a counter-attack or rebuttal in the aftermath to strengthen the claim even further. Despite claims and premises usually being connected through causal links, arguments distinguish themselves from formal logic through their defeasibility. Therefore, a premise does not necessarily have to be fact-based, but could be of rhetorical or subjective nature instead, for instance “*people who get vaccinated are heroes*”. An example argumentative structure formalized in the claim-premise model can be found in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2: The claim-premise model following [82].

Toulmin model. For the British philosopher Stephen Toulmin, the claim-premise representation of arguments did not go far enough. His 1958 publication “*the uses of argument*” [91] is probably the most influential work in the field of argument representation. In the Toulmin model, arguments are formalized as a conversational process between a proponent defending his claim and an opponent, trying to attack. Toulmin defines six functional roles forming an argument, as depicted in Figure 2.3. The premise is called “*grounds*” or “*data*” in this model. It is a fact that logically leads to the claim. New in this model is the role of the warrant, justifying, why and how the grounds support the claim by giving a generally true rule of inference. The warrant can be pictured as a property of the support relation between grounds and claim. Further, the warrant can be strengthened by a backing. The purpose of the backing is to solidify the degree of truthfulness of the warrant. It is typically formulated in a very general manner, which could be in the form of a tautologic statement or law of physics. The next functional role in Toulmin’s model is the modal qualifier. The qualifier specifies the likelihood of the claim holding, e.g. how meaningful and sound the claim is. Earlier, the claim’s defeasibility in argumentative dialogues was mentioned. The target of defeasibility as introduced in the Toulmin model is called the rebuttal. A Toulmin rebuttal is an exception or weakness of the claim, the spot, which the opponent would attack.

Figure 2.3: The Toulmin model following [27].

Freeman model. Due to the Toulmin model’s prominence, it was also criticized a lot. Freeman adapted the Toulmin model in 1991 to answer his major criticisms, including handling of complex argumentation structures, the distinction of roles and the opponent’s representation [66]. Thus, the Freeman model contains some adjustments to the Toulmin Model. Inspired by argument diagramming techniques, Freeman aims at the macrostructure of arguments, not only through the embedding of an argument in a hypothetical dialogue environment, but also through the connection between arguments [28]. In this manner, the Freeman model subsumes grounds and warrant under the term “*premise*”. So, the backing is no component of the argument, but an interface for further supporting arguments. Moreover, in the Freeman model, the modality is not attached to the claim itself but to the relation between premise and claim to concise the structure.

Walton’s argumentation schemes. An entirely different aligned view on argument structure is given by the argumentation schemes of Walton [99], which should not be overseen due to their detail and practical relevance. The Walton schemes focus on the route of reasoning an argument uses for persuasion. In the Toulmin model, the schemes would presumably be related to the warrant role. According to the three routes of reasoning “*deduction*”, inference from the general to the specific, “*induction*”, inference from the specific to the general, and “*abduction*”, inference through understanding discovery, Walton developed a catalog of argument types, each one consisting of a set of premises, assumptions and exceptions, which can be challenged by their respective set of critical questions or defeasibility conditions [98].

Figure 2.4 shows some of the argument types, one of which is the “*argument by example*”. The premise states that in a specific case, an individual shows two properties. The conclusion infers inductively, that each individual showing the first property, must also show the second. Such argument can be attacked using one of the following five critical questions: “*is the proposition claimed in the premise in fact true?*”, “*does the example cited support the generalization it is supposed to be an instance of?*”, “*is the example typical of the kinds of cases the generalization covers?*”, “*how strong is the generalization?*” and “*do special circumstances of the example impair its generalizability?*”. The Walton schemes are successfully implemented in the AraucariaDB project [73].

Type of reasoning	Deductive axioms	Induction	Abduction
Type of argument	Argument from definition, genus...	Argument from example	Argument from (improper) signs
	Argument from cause to effect	...	Practical reasoning
	Argument from consequences	...	Argument from best explanation
	Argument from commitment

Figure 2.4: Walton’s argumentation schemes following [55].

To summarize the subchapter, there is a diversity of perspectives to represent the architecture of arguments, so that no clear consensus is given except for the distinction between claim and premise. All of the models examined above focus on the understanding of argument structure from a reasoning or dialogue point of view, none of them include the work with textual sequences. Which argument model to decide for highly depends on the goal at hand. As a consequence, the following section is dedicated to notions of argumentation that are already applied in different disciplines dealing with linguistic data.

2.2.2 Argumentation across Disciplines

As argumentation theory was not developed with ADU detection in mind, the next section examines the usage of arguments in several domains typically working with text, that is, the legal domain, the domain of teaching as well as the domain of scientific writing.

Law. A domain where arguments are the bread and butter of their employees is the domain of law. One of the first concepts that students in German law schools learn is the distinction between two writing styles: appraisal style and judgment style [92]. Both styles make use of the legal syllogism dating back to Aristotle, a form of deductive reasoning, starting with a major premise, which is then chained to a minor premise, leading to the final conclusion [83].

- All men are mortal. (*major premise*)
- Socrates is a man. (*minor premise*)
- Therefore, Socrates is mortal. (*conclusion*)

Similarly, the appraisal style assumes a hypothesis, often expressed in its subjunctive form and citing the underlying legal norms. Subsequently, the definition is expressed in appraisal style. In Table 2.2, the definition is expressed as a simple if-then inference, but the definition could also encompass other conditions to be met, such as specifications of abstract legal constructs. The actual inference step happens in the subsumption, where the abstract legal term is applied to the present information. In the subsumption, all the available information has to be brought in to persuade the audience. At the end of an argument in appraisal style, the drawn conclusion is stated [101]. Drawing the line to the claim-premise model from the previous subchapter, the appraisal style consists of the transition from premises to claim.

Appraisal style		Judgment style	
Hypothesis	<i>It might have rained.</i>	Conclusion	<i>It has rained.</i>
Definition	<i>If the road is wet, it has rained.</i>	Definition	<i>If the road is wet, it has rained.</i>
Subsumption	<i>Today, the road is wet.</i>	Subsumption	<i>The conditions are met. Today, the road is wet.</i>
Conclusion	<i>Hence, it has rained.</i>		

Table 2.2: Appraisal style and judgment style in German law following [92].

The opposed order of claim and premise can be found in judgment style. The writing style practiced in legal judgments starts by giving the conclusion. In contrast to the appraisal style, the argument should not contain every information from any angle, instead should only consider the relevant information, comparable to a “*lazy evaluation*” in computer science. The judgment style consists of only three steps. After the legal consequences are given, the requirements are checked in a determination sentence and finally the concrete facts are stated [19]. As a highly formalized domain, legal documents already served as targets for AM studies [61].

Essay writing. Another field where clear structural best practice is given to generate text is the writing of persuasive essays. Similar to law, it is a popular domain for the computational extraction of argument structures [9]. To identify ADUs using sequence labeling at the token level, for example, Stab and Gurevych [82] gave students the task to write down their opinion on a given argumentative topic such as “*competition or cooperation—which is better*”. Language students who are writing an essay are facing two major challenges: the generating of ideas to a given argumentative topic and the composition of the ideas into written text to efficiently communicate their stance [36]. One best practice taught to enhance convinciveness is the usage of the reasons-counterargument structures as illustrated in Table 2.3. After an introduction, building the common ground with the reader and setting up the argumentative thesis stating the author’s stance, the reasoning paragraphs follow. Each reasoning paragraph contains a topic sentence, suitable evidence and explanation as well as a wrap-up [81]. Building an argumentative outline, the writers have a choice between two routes of persuasion. The first one, depicted on the left, consecutively presents a pro-argument, a counterargument, and the refutation thereof. The second scheme repeatedly alternates between pro-arguments and refutation of counterarguments. Both routes close with a summarizing conclusion paragraph.

Reasons followed by counterarguments	Alternating reasons and counterarguments
I. Introduction	I. Introduction
II. First Reason	II. First Reason
III. Second Reason	III. Refute Counterarguments
IV. <i>n</i> th Reason	IV. Second Reason
V. Refute Counterarguments	V. Refute Counterarguments
VI. Conclusion	VI. Continue Pattern
	VI. Conclusion

Table 2.3: Common structures of the persuasive essay.

Scientific Articles. Van Dijk [94] suggests that papers in the experimental sciences follow an argumentative superstructure. In scientific communities, communicative acts between authors take place, using the same headers, such as “*introduction*”, “*method*”, “*results*” and “*discussion*”, to claim a research goal, which is justified by a sound evaluation to achieve persuasiveness, for instance in the shape of good reviews and numerous publications. Thereupon builds Teufel’s Argumentative Zoning (AZ), which is perceived as the predecessor of AM [87]. The work is based on the idea to classify sentences as one of the disjunctive, research-field-agnostic argumentative zones, which are summarized in Table 2.4. Sentences in the scientific article are divided in this manner after their intellectual property. The purpose of writing a research paper is hence the claim of ownership on knowledge (Knowledge Claim, KC). “*Aim*” and “*Textual*” describe sentences that belong to the author with the “*Aim*” describing the specific research goal and “*Textual*” describing structural information as in a chapter overview. “*Background*”, “*Basis*”, “*Contrast*” and “*Other*” are related to somebody else’s KC with “*Background*” capturing common knowledge, “*Basis*” as knowledge the paper seeks to extend, “*Contrast*” as dissociation and critique of

Category	Description
Aim	<i>Statement of research goal.</i>
Background	<i>Description of generally accepted background knowledge.</i>
Basis	<i>Existing KC provides basis for new KC.</i>
Contrast	<i>An existing KC is contrasted, compared or presented as weak.</i>
Other	<i>Description of existing KC.</i>
Own	<i>Description of any other aspect of new KC.</i>
Textual	<i>Indication of paper's textual structure.</i>

Table 2.4: Argumentative zones in scientific writing following 88.

related work, and "Other" as neutral description of related work. Every other aspect of the new KC is categorized as "Own". Further, Clyne [15] identifies cultural differences in scientific writing. As such, German work captures attention through expressing the concrete results late in the text, whereas English work tends to express their results early on.

Argumentation can be successfully mapped to sentence level as it is already done in practice. In law, principles of logic are applied, with opposing inference order playing a role. In essay writing, structural attributes such as refutation add to persuasiveness. Scientific communication itself can also be seen as a form of argumentation, defending a KC. The next section will make the transition to Computer Science, examining the procedural extraction of arguments from text data, Argument Mining.

2.2.3 Argument Mining Task

Argument Mining aims at automatically extracting structured arguments from unstructured textual documents [54]. These textual documents may reside in various domains, such as legal judgments, persuasive essays and scientific publications as seen above. Resulting from such variety, miscellaneous research areas are tackling with the extraction of arguments in recent years. Lippi and Torroni [54] endeavored to collect and classify different approaches in a unified AM pipeline architecture. According to them, the AM process depends on the genre of data, the granularity, dedicating whether arguments should be found on the document-, paragraph-, sentence or intra-sentence level, the argument's structure and the goal of the analysis. Further subdividing the AM pipeline into a total of seven steps is the work of Stede et al. [83] (to be compared in the following).

1. Identify argumentative text.
2. Segment the text into ADUs.
3. Identify the central claim.
4. Identify the role/function of ADUs.
5. Identify relations between ADUs.
6. Build the overall structural representation.
7. Identify the type and the quality of the argumentation.

Identification of argumentative text. At first, textual data of the chosen granularity have to be identified as argumentative. Surely, not every text portion in the area of interest shows argumentative quality. Some judgments contain pure non-argumentative summaries of events. In scientific papers, the description of results should be neutrally formulated. Political speeches typically contain a number of acknowledgments of farewells. Blog posts are often opinionated but not logically justified. Thus, in the first step of the AM task, a text portion’s argumentative quality is identified. To this end, a notion of argumentativeness is needed as a scientific base to support this intuition. Wachsmuth [97] resolves this issue by giving the following definition. “*A text should be seen as argumentative if you think that it explicitly or implicitly conveys the stance of the speaker in some controversial issue.*” So, first, there has to be a stance, indicating the proponent’s attitude towards a controversial topic, differentiating the statement from written accounts, and second, the stance also has to be conveyed, hence a certain backing or justification is needed for a text portion to be argumentative. The assignment of text portions to an argumentative property can be executed as a standard ML classification task.

Segmentation into ADUs. The second step in the AM task consists of the argumentative text portion being segmented into smaller ADUs. Stede [83] defines an ADU as a “*span of text that plays a single role for the argument being analyzed, and is demarcated by neighboring text spans that play a different role or none at all*”. The notion given in the AM framework can be seen as abstract as the step depends on the chosen argumentative granularity, e.g. size of the text spans identified as argumentative in the previous step (documents, paragraphs, sentences) and on the roles of the atomic units to be analyzed, e.g. which part of the text portion contains the claim of the argument and which part of the portion supports or attacks the claim. The roles of ADUs are defined by the underlying argument structure from chapter 2.2.1. Three common approaches facing the segmentation problem are free annotation, syntax parsers or assumption of a basic unit. In a free annotation, human annotators can freely determine start- and endpoints of an ADU. This method might seem attractive due to its high flexibility, but it also comes with a lot of effort and ambiguity. A syntax parser as used in 68 offers the opportunity to target precise granularity levels such as clauses. As a machine-based approach, it is very systematic, yet also requires a domain with a uniform language and structure or further preprocessing effort to capture real-world language data. A huge body of work follows the third approach, which simply assumes a granularity such as sentences as the default unit representing ADUs. This approach is not as flexible as the former two, but provides some simplicity and allows it to resolve ambiguities through additional definition effort, for instance mapping ADUs to sentences. This work combines steps one and two of the AM task, by implementing a multiclass classifier to identify ADUs as well as non-argumentative passages.

Identification of central claim. Step three of the AM pipeline is the identification of the central claim. Especially in written argumentation, there is one statement that summarizes the essence of the author’s intention. This statement is called the “*central claim*”. It forms the root of the argument graph, since all other arguments are designed to support the major claim. Its identification can thus be crucial to determine the stance of all arguments found in a document. From a practical point of view, this step assumes an explicit claim to be expressed properly. Apart from

closed environments such as online debate forums or student essays, central claims are not to be found easily. In newspapers or speeches, it is common knowledge to find the major claim by reading between the lines. Nevertheless, to formalize an argumentation graph, the major claim is elementary as it adds a hierarchy component to the argumentation.

Identification of ADU functions and relations. In the fourth step, the function of ADUs is determined. It is intertwined with the fifth step, "*identification of relations*" between ADUs, since both are based on the structure in which the arguments are represented. In a simple claim-premise model, ADUs are just conclusions and their support, but when extended to more extensive argument models, the ADUs can be scrutinized by their dynamics, leading to sophisticated insights. Specified argument functions can be "*support*" or "*attack*", which can also be combined with argumentative roles, indicating whether a claim is made by a "*proponent*" or an "*opponent*" given a stance. Taking the Walton schemes [98] as an example, the function of an ADU could be formalized as a specified route of persuasion, e.g. "*argument by example*". Step five marks the transition from discourse units to discourse relation. As mentioned earlier, the course of argumentation can be easily formalized in a hierarchical tree structure. As such, the central claim would form the root node, whereas all other nodes represent the other ADUs within the collection. The types of nodes are classified in step number four and the edges between the nodes represent the relations between and within arguments. The easiest representation of relations between ADUs are support and attack relations but depending on the argumentation model more complex relations, such as counterattacks ("*rebuttal*") and counter-counterattacks ("*refutation*") emerge. The detection of these edges enabling the spanning of the argumentation tree is conducted in the fifth step of the AM pipeline.

Representation building. Step number six builds the overall structural representation of the argumentation graph. As nodes are given due to steps two and three and edges are given due to step four and five, the sixth step subsequently aggregates the identified argumentation in the final argument graph for further analysis. The usage of tree or graph structures enables the connection of further analysis tools, such as AIFdb [5], where argument maps are processed as a visualized ontology. Moreover, graph-based similarity measures can be applied to reason on the arguments, which leads to the seventh and final step of the AM pipeline: the assessment of argumentation. The last step is highly dependent on the AM goal. On the ready-built argumentation graph, several applications have been conducted. Fields yielding on notions of argumentation quality include consistency checking [12] or the measurement of convincingness [34, 96]. This concludes the overview of AM. The following section continues with the Transformer, the NLP approach that is used to encounter the ADU detection.

2.3 The Transformer

2.3.1 Transfer Learning in NLP

Technological change and innovation are occasionally driven by copy. As genetic algorithms are inspired by Darwin's theories, deep neural networks (NN)s are inspired by the wiring of the human brain, recent developments in Language modeling are inspired by human transfer learning. Transfer learning describes the psychological concept when a pattern or strategy is learned in one context and applied in another [18]. For instance, an athlete learns how repetitive practice enhances his play and reuses this pattern in his academic career. In NLP, the role of transfer was recognized early on and has recently been more relevant than ever.

The first idea that emerged is feature-based pretraining. In this approach, the reusable knowledge is encoded in the word representations using NNs. The most famous representative of this approach is word2vec [59], which uses an embedding-algorithm to transform character-based words into vectors of floats. The vocabulary, as an enumeration of all words used in a set of training data, spans a vector space, in which all words can be expressed by their position and angle to each other. Interestingly, in vector space, even arithmetic operations express syntactic and semantic relationships as for example "*Berlin*" - "*Germany*" + "*France*" = "*Paris*". Nevertheless, these vector representations still struggle with idiomatic phrases such as "*it's a piece of cake*" and do not consider any word order, hence Peters et al. [69], extended the embeddings by a notion of linguistic context. To disambiguate the meaning of a word or phrase in a given context, the word's environment, that is, the sentence it occurs in, has to be known. For instance, the sentence "*The bank had a beautiful view over the river*" describes a different semantic as the sentence "*She worked in this bank for two years*". Therefore, the contextualized representations of ELMo (Embeddings from Language Models) contain functions of whole input sentences per word. Other than that, the ELMo embeddings were trained on two language modeling tasks. A language modeling task has the objective to predict the next word. As text data are sequences of words and no further labels are needed to make the predictions, these tasks are called semi-supervised tasks, referencing to Machine Learning (ML) tasks, either being supervised (each data entry has a class, "*label*" assigned to it) or being non-supervised (data entries have no labels, but can be classified due to universal distance metrics). In this manner, ELMo was trained on one task, predicting the next word, "*left-to-right (LTR) context*", and on a second task, predicting the previous word, "*right-to-left (RTL) context*". Word embeddings and contextual word embeddings are both a useful and reusable abstraction, but are in need of task-specific architectures to perform across NLP tasks. Hence, they are not instantly applicable to every domain, hence they are no direct equivalent to human transfer learning.

Thereafter, transfer learning shifted to encoding the reusable knowledge in the classifier, which is called pretraining by fine-tuning. An example of this approach is Howard and Ruder's Universal Language Model Fine-tuning for Text Classification (ULMFiT) [42]. They take an idea practiced in computer vision since 2013 and applied it for NLP along with some fine-tuning practices. Instead of training NNs from scratch with randomly initialized weights, already trained weights are loaded. The pretrained weights do not have to originate in the exact same dataset, a loosely similar domain is sufficient. Based on a Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) architecture, the authors further fine-tuned their NN by means of two techniques,

capitalizing from the insight that the first layers of the NN contain more general information and the last layers contain more specific information of the features. First, they freeze the general layers in the backpropagation to only update the task-specific last layer. Second, they use discriminate learning rates, to update the final layers at a higher pace during further training. The term pretraining therefore refers to the training before the saving of the weights to be reused. The according post-training, also called downstream training, is the actual fine-tuning of the classifier for the NLP task the model has to solve. As the last layers are replaceable and therefore task-agnostic because the number of output neurons can be chosen for the task at hand, this approach is analog to human transfer learning.

The breakthrough of transfer learning however came with BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) [20] in 2018, disrupting the state of the art in eleven language understanding tasks using bidirectional masked language modeling. As opposed to ULMFiT, BERT is not LSTM-based but based on the Transformer architecture by Vaswani et al. [95], solving the long-term dependencies issues of LSTMs and further explained in the following section. Before BERT, multilayered architectures could only be trained unidirectionally, because else words had information on themselves, with the consequence that the model would easily train but lack the capability to predict. For this reason, ELMo embeddings were trained in two directions and the resulting models were concatenated afterward. BERT solves this difficulty by pretraining via a Masked Language Modeling (MLM) task. In the MLM task, 15% of the tokens were randomly replaced by a masked token, which is then the target of prediction. Besides the MLM task, BERT was also trained by a Next Sentence Prediction (NSP) task, as used for question answering. The next sections cope with the transformer, whose encoder stacks are used for BERT's architecture and some underlying concepts such as attention, positional encodings and feedforward neural networks (FFNN).

2.3.2 Transformer Architecture

In the following, the architecture of the Transformer [95], which is used for BERT and other language models, is shown. In general, the model receives an input in the shape of a list of fixed-sized word embeddings. Their composition and peculiarities is the topic of section 2.3.4. The Transformer’s output is a probability distribution over a set of output classes depending on the task, for instance the vocabulary to predict which word follows in a sequence. As described earlier, the task to be applied is fine-tunable to different tasks through transfer learning.

Figure 2.5: The Transformer - model architecture following [95].

The encoder-decoder architecture of the Transformer is illustrated in Figure 2.5, taken from the original Transformer’s paper [95]. The encoder-stack is composed of N layers. The N given in Vaswani et al. equals six and is often chosen in related work for comparability reasons. Each layer is again subdivided into two subsequent layers. One layer handles the multi-head attention mechanism, building a feature space through content-based querying, which distinguishes the Transformer from other architectures and is therefore treated in its own subchapter 2.3.3. The attention sublayer prepares the data to be fed to the subsequent layer. The other sublayer contains a fully-connected feedforward neural network (FFNN), which possesses neither recurrence nor convolution mechanism, hence needs appropriately prepared input data to process not one word at a time but a weighted word aggregation. The sublayers share a residual connection to avoid gradient vanishing and each sublayer is followed by a normalization step.

The decoder stack also comprises N layers. As BERT models only rely on an encoder stack due to their masking technique, they don't implement the decoder side. However, the decoder is to be mentioned for completeness. Additionally to the encoder, the decoder comprises a sublayer taking care of encoder-decoder attention, so that the model cannot see current and later positions. It takes the input from the Encoder and generates a vector of symbols as output, one element at a time.

2.3.3 Attention

As Vaswani et al. stated in the title of their paper "*Attention is all you need*" [95], the attention mechanics play an important role in the workings of the Transformer, next to the classifier itself and the input data.

Over a long period of time, NLP systems had trouble dealing with long-term references as occurring in every-day communication. For instance, when two friends meet and have a talk, it is very common for them to reference old events and stories and to immediately recall the background¹. Such linguistic references used to be hard for NLP systems to make before the Transformer since they require huge amounts of memory and tinkering. One benchmark challenge for NLU is the Winograd Schema [53]. Given the statement "*the animal didn't cross the street, because it was too tired*", a human listener instantly knows which entity the pronoun "*it*" refers to: to the animal. This is clear, because due to common sense it is known that the animal is a living being and as such goes through different states such as being hungry or being tired, but the machine has no common sense and needs to know which words to focus on. Even having identified the word classes, it is not clear which noun the pronoun refers to: "*street*" or "*animal*". So, in order to solve a Winograd Schema, the model needs to know which word to focus on although the context-giving words are not always adjacent and therefore have to be kept in memory. For LSTMs, this is a limitation since dealing with over 1000 words causes the gradient to vanish. Convolutional neural networks (CNN)s handle this more efficiently by using positional information, yet leave some room for improvement. The Transformer, on the contrary, solves this problem through the usage of content-based querying, called "*attention*". The idea is similar to that of context in ELMo. The encoder reads the input sentence and builds a representation of each token. Therefore, it uses a dot product similarity between the word that is currently processed (query Q) and the words in the sentence around it (keys K) to determine which word is most relevant for the current context. This relevance information is then used to weigh up or down the value V , which is later fed to the NN, after some downscaling by dimension of the input vector (d_k) and a normalization by absolute extent of the value (*softmax*). Formula 2.1 summarizes the attention calculation using two matrix multiplications and normalization.

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V \quad (2.1)$$

Paying respect to multiple grammatical dependencies (e.g. noun suffixes in translation tasks that depend on both the gender and the number as seen in chapter 2.1.1) and the variation of relevant dependencies according to the NLP task to be

¹"Attentional neural networks" talk. Last retrieved 01.31.2021 from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rBCqOTefxvg>

solved, the attention mechanism is computed simultaneously for h sets of query, key and value matrices, called attention heads. Each head uses different linear transformations in order to learn different relationships. After the computation of each head's output matrices, the outputs are concatenated and dense. As encoder-sided and decoder-sided attention vary in the usage of masks, encoder-self-attention, encoder-decoder attention and decoder-self-attention can be distinguished. Figure 2.6 highlights the focus of a translation-task-trained attention head from an encoder layer, correctly exploiting the pronoun information from the Winograd schema example. Moreover, the input data are given a positional element to further refine the attention mechanism, which is clarified in the section to come.

Figure 2.6: Attention following [44].

2.3.4 Positional Encoding

Earlier, the attention mechanism by content-based querying using a weighted average was demonstrated. Whilst forming a weighted average might be handy to keep long-term dependencies, it also sacrifices the positional information of each token. As each word is processed in parallel, a lot of training time can be saved, allegedly at the cost of word order notion. This shortcoming is solved by the encoding of input data. At the bottom of the encoder and decoder, word embeddings of fixed size are handed to the Transformer. Before this happens, the relative position of a word in a sentence is formalized by a second positional embedding, typically using a sine or cosine function of different frequencies. As the positional embeddings and word embeddings share the same size, both tensors are added to each other to consecutively be given to the model. After the input data design, the classifier is shortly portrayed.

2.3.5 Feedforward Neural Network

To close with the Transformer architecture and thereby with the technical background chapter, the classifier, which encapsulates the learning, is briefly covered to have an intuition for the experiments. Classification tasks, as the assignment from

text segments to ADUs in this case, are a part of supervised ML. For large amounts of teaching inputs, neural networks deliver accurate classification results. In the presented architecture, a classical fully-connected feedforward neural network is placed in every encoder and decoder layer as well as in the final linear layer. FFNNs are the simplest form of neural networks. Neurons, small computation units, are aligned in an input layer, an output layer and a number of hidden layers in between (see Figure 2.7). The term “*fully-connected*” refers to the edges between the neurons on consecutive layers so that every neuron of a following layer knows the activations of all the neurons of the previous layer. In order for the FFNN to make accurate predictions, for instance, to recognize a sentence as argumentative, the minimization of a cost function, typically cross-entropy, is essential. To achieve this goal, three components are necessary: a forward phase generating an output of the net, a teaching input giving the net a cue on the distance to the desired output and a backpropagation phase updating the network using gradient descent [86]. In the forward phase, each j th neuron in the l th layer has an activation function as shown in Formula 2.2. The strength of the connection between neuron j and its direct predecessor neuron i is expressed by the weight $w_i^{l,j}$. Moreover, each neuron has a bias b_j^l , which is the tendency of the neuron to be activated or not. Hence, the activation of a neuron (from the second layer on) depends on the function f itself, the weighted sum of the activation of the previous neurons and a bias.

$$a_j^l = f\left(\sum_i (w_i^{l,j} a_i^{l-1}) + b_j^l\right) \quad (2.2)$$

These weights and biases are randomly initialized for standard FFNNs or are already set for pretrained NNs, leading to an output still containing failure. Then, the produced, faulty output is compared to the desired output from the training data by means of a cost function, typically cross entropy. Afterward, the backpropagation phase minimizes this cost function by recursively updating weights and biases of the net using the gradient descent method. In each backpropagation phase, the model takes a step following the negative gradient of the cost function in the direction of the steepest descent in the search space of weights and biases. The size of these steps is determined by the learning rate η and should converge towards zero to find a local minimum.

Figure 2.7: Fully-connected feedforward neural network following [72].

2.4 Related Work

The related work section addresses the research gap by identifying strengths and weaknesses of the present body of research. Building on the linguistic, argumentative and technical knowledge from the previous sections, we first examine papers that execute steps of the AM pipeline cross-lingually 2.4.1, then narrow the scope to lines of work for French and German 2.4.2 and finally scrutinize the upcoming domain of cross-lingual AM profiting from pretrained LMs 2.4.3.

2.4.1 Cross-lingual AM

This section focuses on work in cross-lingual AM building on parallel corpora. Up to our knowledge, the field of cross-lingual AM was started by Peldszus and Stede [67]. With their microtext corpus, they introduced the first bilingual dataset incorporating argument annotations. Given are 112 microtext containing 567 ADUs on subsentence level. In a controlled text generation experiment, subjects are asked to produce answers to a question of the format “*Should one do X?*”. The resulting texts are short, yet complete in a sense that they possess a standpoint and a justification. The original data are recorded in German, then professionally translated into English. On their microtext corpus, Peldszus and Stede conduct a set of four AM tasks: relation prediction, central claim identification, role identification and function identification with the role varying between “*proponent*” and “*opponent*”, and the simplified function varying between “*support*” and “*attack*”. They build an evidence graph to predict the structure’s aspects using a minimum spanning tree algorithm. Although the work is from 2015, it is still relevant as lots of multilingual work presented below extend the corpus. The microtext corpus is a meaningful data source that is built from scratch and manually annotated. The only minor point of critique consists in the artificial assumption that every sentence is argumentative. One line of work building on Peldszus and Stede is Namor et al. [62]. The authors conduct the same four AM subtasks in Italian. In the first phase, the original German data are translated to Italian using the DeepL translation software. In the second phase, the machine-translated corpus was manually checked and corrected as needed. This is necessary because the 2019 version of DeepL proposed the most common translation, which was not necessarily the most suitable. Since the machine translation is sentence-aligned, the data could be changed to Italian by just one-to-one replacing the sentences in the XML file. Additionally, for the adaption to Italian, an upgrade of spaCy and Python was made as well as the implementation of Italian connectives, describing part type, syntactic type and relation type. The AM results, particularly in the function classification, are slightly weaker as the results from the English-German dataset, yet the translation approach seems successful. Namor et al. create no own proper corpus, they only further translate the microtext corpus. This might not contribute to a versatile argumentative notion but definitely contributes to comparability.

Even so relying on Peldszus and Stede’s microtext corpus is the paper of Fishcheva and Kotelnikov [26]. They execute a binary sentence classification predicting “*pro*” and “*con*” labels for the Russian Language. Their entire experiment conduction is systematic and comprehensively written. Four contributions are delivered by the paper: (1) the publication of a Russian argumentative corpus, (2) the analysis of the influence of various feature types, (3) the analysis of influence of various classifiers and (4) the comparison of machine translation systems against a human gold

standard. The authors start with the identification of the most effective feature-classifier combinations, training on the human annotated data, then train the best combination on machine-translated Russian texts. Seven feature types are scrutinized including positional features, lexical features (discourse markers), punctuation features, n-grams, contextual features regarding left and right context, tf-idf features and word2vec features. The latter two were not recommended as they showed themselves ineffective for the task while the best results were delivered by contextual features followed by lexical features. Concerning the six classifiers, support vector machines (SVM) and classifier ensembles brought the best results with Bagging reaching a macro-averaged F1 of 0.714. Finally, Google Translate’s machine translation outperformed the Yandex Translate version, which again outperformed the Prompt translation. The classifier performance on the Google Translate data was even competitive with human-translated data. Following the positive results achieved by the contextual embeddings, the work already contains some transfer learning aspects. Also, though only a translation of the microtext corpus, the involvement of human translators in the workflow stands out positively.

Furthermore, Sliwa et al. [80] contribute the first argumentative parallel corpora targeting Turkish, Greek, Albanian, Croatian, Serbian, Macedonian, Bulgarian, Romanian and Arabic. The task performed in their work is a binary argumentative sentence detection to automatically annotate their newly developed corpora. Corresponding to the first step in the AM pipeline, sentences are classified as either “*argumentative*” or “*non-argumentative*”. To this purpose, the authors use eight not further specified ML classifiers (SVM, decision trees and a CNN are reported). However, the classifiers are trained on the English source language based on manually-annotated articles of the Guardian, a persuasive essay corpus and a Wikipedia corpus. For the projection phase, two corpora are exploited: the South-East European Times corpus retrieved from a multilingual news website for the Balkan Languages and a collection of 3543 heuristically sentence-aligned multilingual articles of the Huffington post for Arabic. The classifiers are evaluated on copies of the English version of the datasets and the target languages’ sentence labels are decided by majority voting using a decision threshold. Single model performances are subsequently evaluated against the majority vote, trivially leading to high recall and precision values according to the threshold. The choice of aggregated model results without including a human baseline seems questionable.

2.4.2 Cross-lingual AM for French and German

After visiting several general approaches for multilingual AM, we examine some papers of even higher relevance for this thesis as they share the same target languages. An interesting line of work is conducted by Eger et al. [23, 24]. In the paper “*Cross-lingual Argumentation Mining: Machine Translation (and a bit of Projection) is All You Need!*” [24] Eger et al. first translate the persuasive student essay corpus by Stab and Gurevych 2014 into German by human translation and machine-translate the corpus to French, Spanish and Chinese with Google Translate. Second, two transfer methods are compared: direct transfer and projection for a token-based sequence tagging with ADUs. In direct transfer, a model based on bilingual word embeddings is trained on labeled data of the source language, then applied to the target language. In projection, human-labeled source language data are aligned with

the target language using fast-align word alignments. The first and last words of a labeled sequence in the source language are identified and the sequence between respective first and last word in the target language is marked with the label. The LSTM can then be trained and evaluated on the target language data. As a result of the cross-lingual experiments, projection performs considerably better than direct transfer, which is struggling with word order.

Thereupon, Eger et al. conduct a second study [23] combining the strengths of the naïve projection and the direct transfer approach on a sentence-level ADU detection task and a token-level PoS tagging task on French and German data. The method is called PD3, according to the three datasets applied, the labeled source language dataset, the pseudo-labeled source language dataset and the pseudo-labeled target language dataset. “*Pseudo-labels*” refer to the labels produced by a model trained on the labeled source language dataset. A PD3-merge and a PD3-multi-task-learning approach are compared, with the PD3 merge approach winning. On a small dataset scenario with 50-500 parallel sentences, both PD3 approaches outperform the isolated transfer. One advantage of the experiments is the presence of a non-argumentative label, enhancing the data’s realism. Eger et al. properly evaluate their machine translation approach and the method is an invaluable contribution to cross-lingual transfer to low-resource languages.

2.4.3 Cross-lingual AM using Transfer Learning

None of the previous work coped with above uses modern transfer learning approaches to deal with multilingual AM. However, there already exists some promising work in the field. Coming from the domain of multilingual stance detection, Vamvas and Sennrich [93] extract a large-scale multi-topic corpus covering Swiss national elections. “*X-stance*” contains 67000 comments on 150 political questions answered by politicians. Retrieved from the app “*Smartvote*”, candidates can give one of the answers “*yes*”, “*rather yes*”, “*rather no*” and “*no*” to the question and an explaining comment. The answers are given in either German, French or Italian depending on the candidate’s background. Worth mentioning is the corpus’s balanced data split. Out of the 12 topics covered, two are held out of the training data to measure cross-topic generalization. To measure cross-language generalization, the smallest language set “*Italian*” is used for evaluation. In addition, 16 questions are left out as well as a percentage of politicians to measure cross-question generalization and cross-respondent generalization. The question-answer pairs are implemented as a sequence pair classification task using a multilingual BERT model, delivering moderately good results. The “*x-stance*” corpus presented by Vamvas and Sennrich is both resourceful and heterogenous for multilingual stance detection. Since the answers are not translated and the data are not aligned, the “*x-stance*” corpus is only found to be a strongly-comparable parallel corpus. Nevertheless, the work profits from a modern language model, turning it into a part of the state of the art.

Rodrigues and Branco perform a sentence-level argument identification task for Portuguese [74]. In their three experiments, they examine Machine Translation with Google Translate, Transfer Learning from Portuguese word-embeddings and multilingual BERT, and text augmenting techniques. The first experiment projects from the UKP Sentential AM Corpus to the translated Portuguese version to apply a BiLSTM with an F-measure of 0.7228. In their second experiment, FastText embeddings, multilingual vectors, GloVe and word2vec representations are compared

with a multilingual BERT model pretrained with adapters, whereof the BERT model reaches the highest accuracy. The data augmentation techniques manage to further enhance the accuracy by 1%. The experiments show that Portuguese is no exception to successful label transfer. Similarly to the transfer approaches from [80] and [62], the results could have been verified through human translators or annotators.

By far the largest experiments scrutinized in this literature research are those of Toledo-Ronen et al. [90] from IBM Research. They perform an analysis of five languages on three AM tasks varying in difficulty using two paradigms, which allows them to draw more wholistic conclusions. The examined languages are German, Spanish, French, Italian and Dutch. The first task is a stance classification, where a stance toward a controversial topic has to be classified. The second task, evidence detection, determines whether a sentence can be used as evidence for a given topic. The third and most complex task in terms of agreement is argumentation quality assessment, where the convincingness of an argument has to be judged. The experiments were conducted based on two pseudo-test sets, which are machine-translated from English datasets from project debater by Watson Translate, and one crowdsourced human-written dataset holding over 10000 arguments in the five languages. Two paradigms are analyzed building on differently pretrained configurations of multilingual BERT: first, the less-efficient "*translate-test*" paradigm, which trains the model on English translations created on prediction time and second, the "*translate-train*" paradigm, in which multilingual BERT is pretrained on concatenated datasets in the multiple target languages. The results are twofold. For stance detection and evidence detection, pretraining on related language groups performs almost as good as pretraining on six language groups. The contrary is shown for argument quality assessment, where with less pretraining languages the performance increases. One key finding leading to these results is that quality is harder to preserve under translation due to switching labels in fields with low confidentiality. The findings are revealing as one might draw the conclusion that there could be several use cases for monolingual and multilingual LMs. Other than in the majority of related work, the study doubts the quality of pure machine-translated test sets. For efficient pretraining configurations in the AM context and beyond, the further scrutiny of synergies between related languages would be compelling to see.

The existing research in cross-lingual AM agrees that efforts should not exclude languages other than English. Although the inspected work is not older than 2015, recent developments in architectures and practices turn a huge part of the research's results obsolete. Although multilingual AM performs well on the known narrowly constructed benchmarks often completely excluding non-argumentative content, more realistic data are a higher obstacle. Toledo-Ronen et al. [90] deliver the only work scrutinized considering languages not only as black boxes, but as versatile structures to be related to one another. Beyond the numerous approaches solving the resource scarcity in cross-lingual AM, various rely on machine translation and projection [24, 62, 80]. Although such approaches shallowly solve the problem, they can only be seen as a second-best since the degree to which they represent real, human-authored text is not measured. It therefore remains open, whether the gained low-priced comparability outweighs the lacking breadth of the benchmarks. Therefore, this work is based on human-translated data from the Europarl corpus, on which human-made annotations are produced that are the target of a classification task executed via modern transfer learning.

3. Method

3.1 Proceedings

Following the theoretical background, as a next step, the practical way of proceedings in this thesis is to be clarified. As the research goal pursued is to compare the quality of German and French ADU detection, both target languages have to be treated uniformly wherever possible to ensure the best possible comparability. Therefore, the method's structure is adapted to the uniform industry standard CRISP-DM, short for cross-industry standard process for data mining [13]. The standard is applicable since the ADU detection task falls under the umbrella term of text mining tasks, which in-turn falls under the umbrella term of data mining tasks. The CRISP-DM framework includes six non-rigid phases, as illustrated in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: CRISP-DM framework following [13].

Phase one is business understanding, meaning in a wider sense, the definition of targets and conceptual understanding. In the present case, no direct business context is given. Instead, underlying concepts originate in the domain of data processing, of linguistics and argumentation theory. These areas are covered in the background chapter 2 and were scrutinized through a literature research.

Phase two of the CRISP-DM framework comprises the data understanding. In this phase, collecting and familiarizing with the data takes place. The data understanding phase is mirrored in chapter "Europarl Corpus" 3.2, summarizing information about the Europarl parallel corpus. Questions explored will be, how procedures in

the European Parliament are done, how the corpus was created, what structure the corpus follows and how it distinguishes itself from other corpora. Furthermore, we identify how the corpus must be edited to suit this thesis’s purpose, which will be executed in the subsequent phase.

In phase three, the data preparation is then executed. According to Chapman et al. [13] the data preparation phase “*covers all activities to construct the final dataset*”. The data preparation activities are subdivided into the three chapters “*Data Sampling*” 3.3, “*ADU Annotation*” 3.4 and “*Further Preprocessing*” 3.5. As the Europarl corpus was not initially designed to capture argument structures, some adjustments must be made. For this reason, a systematic sampling must be conducted, appropriately trimming the corpus in size, which allows to manually annotate the corpus with the needed ADU annotations. Further, typical syntactic harmonization steps are applied to the subcorpus. Here, particular differences between German and French preprocessing are highlighted whenever they occur.

Phase four is the modeling phase, in which models are selected and applied. The selection of language models can be found in chapter 3.6. Models are selected based on whether they are a state-of-the-art LM, their free availability for academic purposes, economical computational resources of the model, an appropriate pretraining objective and feature level and the capability to cope with different languages. The application includes a downstream learning and tuning phase to optimally put the chosen LMs into practice on the ADU detection task. The ADU detection experiments are realized in chapter 3.7.

The fifth phase in the CRISP-DM framework consists of the evaluation, as shown in chapter 4. The evaluation is made based on metrics such as F-measure, evaluation loss and MCC to answer the hypotheses. Subsequently the bilingual ADU results are compared against English classification and language models.

The sixth and final phase of the CRISP-DM framework is called “*deployment*”. This phase aims to bring out the practical value of the scrutinized models and patterns. Again, this thesis is not set in a business context, hence a direct equivalent to the deployment phase in a narrow sense is missing. However, the gained insights will be further evaluated and discussed in the bigger picture in chapter 5. Thus, the final deployment aspect of going beyond the method is given through discussion and outlook.

3.2 Europarl Corpus

After the method’s structure is outlined, the next pages contain a short analysis of the Europarl Corpus by Koehn [50], which delivers the data, forming the foundation of this work. Familiarization with the data is crucial to generate convincing, meaningful and after all interpretable insights and serves as the basis for sound decision support throughout the entire workflow. The data are organized as a corpus, a “*collection of related documents that contain natural language*” [3]. In case of the Europarl corpus, the related documents are minutes extracted of the debates of the European Parliament. Furthermore, the content is syntactically encoded in the different languages of the European Union (EU), which makes the corpus interesting for multilingual studies. The latest version of the Europarl data was downloaded from the OPUS website [45] containing raw text data surrounded by XML tags about speakers, original language, session IDs and further metadata. As this section portrays the data understanding phase of the adapted CRISP-DM framework, it is

targeted to give a thorough overview of the data. Section 3.2.1 gives an introduction to translation processes in the European Parliament. Section 3.2.2 covers the transition from spoken language over written minutes to crawled text data. Section 3.2.3 highlights the corpus structure according to an array of corpus key figures and section 3.2.4 concludes with the relevance of the chosen corpus as means to compare German and French ADU detection.

3.2.1 Translation in the European Parliament

First and foremost, the data's origin lies within the European institution of legislation, the European Parliament. Debates in the European Parliament are multilingual or as the Italian author Umberto Eco infamously stated "*the language of Europe is translation*" (compare in the following²). The challenge of the translation service in the European Parliament becomes visible when observing the human resources subordinate to the Directorate-General for logistics and interpreting. The translation service of the European Parliament comprises 700 translators, responsible for the translation of legal documents and written language and 270 interpreters, responsible for the simultaneous translation of spoken meetings and debates as well as 1500 outsourced interpreters, who are summoned on demand for larger events³. The Directorate-General for logistics and interpreting is responsible for the linguistic, technical and logistical support for the organization of parliamentary meetings and conferences. Besides plenary sittings, interpreting is also provided in committee and delegation meetings from and into the official languages used and requested by the Member. Its mission includes first to guarantee access to the legislative documents in all official languages, to ensure legitimacy and transparency of the processes of the EU. Second, each language should be treated equally, as to give every citizen the right to communicate in their mother tongue and third the supply of the translation services has to be as efficient and effective as possible following predefined standards. The mission comes with a vision, which is the principle of controlled full multilingualism protecting the European value of cultural and linguistic diversity as documented in article 22 of the EU-Charta. The principle of multilingualism is fulfilled in a bidirectional manner. As a means of participation, each citizen of age can let himself be nominated as a deputy, therefore having the right to speak their own language in the plenaries and meetings. To guarantee full transparency, each citizen is provided the possibility both to follow and to access the parliament's work. Hence, the removal of language barriers is highly prioritized in the European Parliament's procedures through translation and interpreting.⁴

Consequently to the Directorate-General for logistics and interpreting mission and vision, the translation procedure follows a structured design. With the EU's enlargement, the complexity of the translation web has improved even so. Having started with four official languages of the founder countries French, German, Dutch and Italian, the linguistic flawlessness of 12 interpreting directions had to be assured as

²The parliament which speaks 24 languages. Last retrieved 01.31.2021 from <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/about-parliament/en/organisation-and-rules/multilingualism>

³Translation. Last retrieved 01.31.2021 from <https://epthinktank.eu/2019/09/11/translation-and-interpretation-at-the-european-parliament/>

⁴The described principle of multilingualism is an interesting contrast to the developments perceived in NLP, since the political perspective defends language diversity while in the more market-driven NLP, some high-resource language communities are in the center of attention, reinforcing an unbalanced growth.

each of the four languages had to be interpreted into the other three. Today, the EU comprises 24 official languages: Bulgarian, Czech, Croatian, Danish, Dutch, English, Estonian, Finnish, French, German, Greek, Hungarian, Italian, Irish, Latvian, Lithuanian, Maltese, Polish, Portuguese, Romanian, Slovak, Slovene, Spanish and Swedish adding up to 552 interpreting edges. Not counted in are translation services to external languages as needed for international relations or the interpretation to sign language.

During a plenary session, the interpreting services render the passive language uttered by the speaker, to the active language of the listener in two phases, called the “*relay*”⁵. To cope with the sum of 24 active and passive languages, 72 interpreters are positioned in ISO-standardized interpreting booths⁶. In the first step, the speech or statement is translated in a widely used language, which can be English, French or German. Subsequently, the translated content will be relayed to the lesser-used languages, distributing the speech to the entire plenary hall. In the relay procedure, French and German are both in the early stage of the interpreting pipeline. Adulterated translation quality should thus not be expected in a disproportional amount. The extensive scope of the translation and interpreting services in the European Parliament also represents itself in the parliament’s cost structure. Over one-third of the Parliament’s expenditures result from multilingualism.

3.2.2 Original Data Source Creation

Corresponding to the principles of multilingualism and transparency, the minutes of the debates of the European Parliament are published online on the parliament’s public relations website⁷. This section covers the extraction of the Europarl Corpus from the initial HTML publications to a sentence aligned multilingual corpus and is entirely based on Koehn’s paper “*Europarl: a Parallel Corpus for Statistical Machine Translation*” [50].

The original Europarl corpus was obtained over a period of approximately six years, starting with 11 languages, upgraded to 21 in the most recent seventh version, naturally changing via more available data and expansion of the underlying political structure. Therefore, the creation of the Europarl Corpus was a long-term project, complicated by changing data formats, standards, other than by growing volume.

At first, the proceedings of the European Parliament were crawled using a web spider. A huge advantage of building a corpus based on governmental data is its straight-forward authorization to process, which is assumably the reason why most parallel corpora are built on data of either international institutions or multilingual countries’ administrations such as those of Canada or Switzerland. In this manner, it is stated that the data is legally accessible, provided that the source is acknowledged. In particular, the authors started on an index page and followed the link structure, including fine-granular steps as each speaker entry had its own page attached, which the authors describe as time-consuming.

After the raw data is obtained, the documents are aligned. For this purpose, connected chunks for all language pairs were extracted and mapped to each other.

⁵Relay. Last retrieved 01.31.2021 from <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/interpretation/en/introduction/introduction.html>

⁶Interpreting. Last retrieved 01.31.2021 from <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/interpretation/en/interpreting-in-the-parliament.html>

⁷Public register website. Last retrieved 01.31.2021 from <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegistreWeb/home/welcome.htm?language=EN>

The HTML scripts were processed using a Perl program that implemented pattern matching to identify the appropriate speakers. The resulting data was stored in day-per-language chunks in a paragraph-aligned format. The data was cleaned for markups. In the following, each linguistic version of the data had to be sentence-split and tokenized according to the rules of its respective grammar. To disambiguate the different usages of periods, e.g. as the end of a sentence or to indicate an abbreviation, a manual whitelisting of common abbreviations in the English, French and German language was executed. Subsequently, some preprocessing measures were taken, which are tailored to the corpus's original purpose, which is SMT. An example for such measure is the transposition of all tokens to lowercase, to eliminate different spellings of the same word, for example when positioned at the beginning of a sentence or when serving as a headline.

In the last step, the alignment level was shifted from the paragraph level to the sentence level. Each paragraph, having a volume of two to five sentences was split into an equal number of sentences for the language pairs using the Gale and Church algorithm [29], matching sentences of similar length and merging them if necessary. Whenever the number of sentences in the bilingual paragraphs to be aligned diverged, the respective paragraph was discarded. The sentence-aligned corpus was also stored on a file-per-language-per-day basis. This ends the scrutinization of the Corpus's creation. In the following section, its qualitative and quantitative composition are analyzed.

3.2.3 Corpus Structure

The Europarl Corpus comprises the proceedings of the European Parliament over a period of almost six years from April 1996 to November 2011. The corpus contains text data in 21 languages spoken in the plenaries of the European Parliament as described in section 3.2.1. The language families represented therein are Romance, Germanic, Finni-Ugric, Baltic and Greek. Since Europarl v3, data is uniformly encoded in UTF-8, short for 8-Bit Universal Coded Character Set Transformation Format. From v3's release on, the corpus was delivered in UTF-8. Since Europarl v5, the corpus also includes minutes in the new eastern European member's languages. In its most recent release Europarl v7, the corpus comprises up to 60 million words per language. The total number of files comes to 207.775 with a number of tokens of 7.59.05 million and a total number of sentence fragments of 30.32 million according to OPUS [45].

Further, a number of corpus features is analyzed to sharpen Europarl's profile as compared to other multilingual corpora. Regarding its genre and register, the corpus is clearly to be put under the heading of politics. The proceedings contain budgetary decisions, votes, persuasive speeches, holiday speeches and organizational agenda items amongst other things. The authors, if this term is applicable, of the corpus's texts are the speakers themselves, optionally their speechwriters or juristic linguists and the interpreters. The topics covered in the speeches range from every aspect of the EU's political competencies, which will be further shown in section 3.3.5. The speeches' intended audience comprises several levels. Initially, the argumentation's proponents and opponents are targeted. Moreover, every attendee of the plenum is addressed in the short term. In the long term, due to the speeches' multichannel publications, the speeches reach a broader audience, every citizen or non-citizen, who wants to inform himself on the parliament's proceedings. The register of the

Europarl corpus can be categorized as “*transcribed spoken*” language or alternatively as “*written to be spoken*” if a speech was prewritten and then just read out by the speaker. Hence, the register could be classified as either “*oral*” or “*written*” language depending on the speaker’s mode of speech and preparation.

The subcorpus relevant to this work is the German-French parallel monolingual XML version. After the removal of markups, the German subcorpus comprises 2.176.537 sentences and 47.236.849 tokens. The French subcorpus is with 2.190,579 sentences and 54.202.850 tokens of comparable size, yet has a higher token-per-sentence ratio ⁸. The ten most frequent unigrams in the German Europarl are as compared to the German Web 2013 corpus: „*Änderungsantrag*“, „*EntschlieÙung*“, „*Berichterstatter*“, „*Mitgliedstaat*“, „*Berichterstatterin*“, „*Kommissarin*“, „*Kommissar*“, „*Ratspräsident*“, „*Kommission*“ and „*EntschlieÙungsantrag*“. The most frequent French tokens as compared to the French Web 2012 corpus also underline Europarl’s tendency towards bureaucracy: “*Commissaire*”, “*États*”, “*Présidente*”, “*rapporteur*”, “*Mesdames*”, “*amendments*”, “*parlement*”, “*Messieurs*”, “*UE*”, “*codécision*” [47].

Cartoni et al. [11] measure the homogeneity of the Europarl corpus using a type-token-ratio as well as lexical density. The standardized type-token ratio is an average over chunks of 1000 tokens, describing the vocabulary’s richness with a high value indicating a broad vocabulary and a low value indicating a specific one. The German-French subcorpus of Europarl reaches a value of 0,3506, which can be categorized as low. This shows that the vocabulary of parliamentary debates costs vocabulary breadth. The other measure lexical density calculates a ratio between lexical items as taken from dictionaries in the respective languages and grammatical items. The lexical density of the German-French Europarl of 0.5569 confirms formal language use. The value turns out similar for different Europarl subcorpora, painting a homogenous picture.

3.2.4 Suitability for the Purpose

After the previous sections have highlighted various aspects of the Europarl Corpus, the following paragraph assesses its suitability for the ADU task. As described earlier, the principle of multilingualism causes translation to be a major endeavor in the European Parliament, leading to a high economical effort and a well-defined translation process, in which German and French are pivot languages. Due to the proceedings’ free availability, Koehn [50] has crawled the Europarl corpus, a high-volume multilingual corpus. The largely UTF-8 encoded corpus is representative of political speeches and homogenous between source and target languages. Building on this knowledge, the suitability of Europarl for bilingual AM can be formulated as follows.

Although the Europarl corpus was designed with an SMT task in mind, it found widespread use in NLP such as for cross-lingual research, frequency analysis, POS tagging and many more [79]. Due to its high volume, the corpus is versatile for various NLP tasks and as such widely exploited, though up to our knowledge not yet for ADU detection. As compared to the European Parliament’s neighboring institution, the European Court for Human Rights (ECHR), which already served as a data basis for research in AM [64], the parliamentary debates of the already collected Europarl corpus promise a higher degree of liveliness, and with it enhanced

⁸Europarl. Last retrieved 01.31.2021 from <https://www.statmt.org/europarl/>

proximity to real-life argumentation. The reason behind Europarl not being used for ADU detection is probably related to the effort of manual annotation and training costs, but with the arrival of transfer learning methods, the latter recently no longer holds. Overall, expanding an acknowledged benchmark corpus such as Europarl for an AM task could be a valid contribution.

Furthermore, Europarl’s genre has high synergy with an AM task. Political speeches are persuasive per se since they are destined to convince an audience, therefore an argumentative stance is automatically given. Even the debates having weaker argumentative stances such as budgetary debates are preparatory to a decision, hence they are compelled to weigh priorities and give reasons, building an argumentative ground. More so, as the data were created in a democratic process, the presence of different interest groups is guaranteed through the parliament’s factions. For all these reasons, Europarl should provide suitable argumentative content.

The last point highlighted in this section and advantageous for the use of Europarl is its multilingual structure. When working with parallel corpora in general, two problems could occur, which Europarl evades due to its structure. Number one, a parallel corpus containing direct translations typically has one source language, which is linguistically unchanged and one target language, edited by at least a translation or interpreting step. [1] describes the difference of the target language compared to its texts when originally produced in the target language as “*Translationese*”, referring to the grammatical differences of the target language which equals a completely new language. Europarl does not share this property. Taking French and German data as an example again, the French data originate from two forms. On one hand it can be originally French, on the other it can be translated French from any other source language. As the same goes for the German version of the corpus, both languages are treated equally. Next to the problem of controlled Translationese, some corpora face another construction challenge. A weakly-comparable parallel corpus is build according to a predefined domain, to which several random samples of different languages are crawled (see chapter 2.1.3). The usage of a corpus designed in this manner is problematic due to a lack of alignment. As the texts are similar, though not identical, the data to be assessed is particularly noisy. Europarl is a fully-parallel corpus, the data are simultaneously collected, covering the identical collection of speeches. As a consequence, fair comparability is given.

The choice for Europarl is based on its acknowledgment as a benchmark, its argumentative content and its favorable multilingual design. In the next sections, tailoring the corpus to the downstream task of this work is to be described.

3.3 Data Sampling

The following section treats the peculiarities of data sampling for the bilingual ADU detection task. At first, some considerations on the need and the means to reduce corpus size are presented 3.3.1, followed by a description of the subsequently executed topic modeling process 3.3.2. The preprocessing steps from chapter 3.3.3 and hyperparameter optimization steps from chapter 3.3.4 lead to topic modeling results 3.3.5, serving as search strings to finally extract the subcorpus, so described in section 3.3.6, as an interim result.

3.3.1 Preliminary Considerations: Criteria to reduce Corpus Size

Human workforce, so needed for manual annotation, is a limited resource. The Europarl Corpus presented in chapter 3.2 comprises data recorded over a time span of 15 years. Due to these restrictions, a rule of thumb in NLP applies to limit manual data processing work on 10% of the original data's scope [7]. Given this assumption, there is still a total amount of every official utterance of the European Parliament over the course of more than a year to face. An endeavor that is too ambitious to be tackled in a master's thesis.

Therefore, other systematic criteria are needed to reduce the corpus size to a volume of less than 10%. One criterion to filter corpus size is "*time*". To reduce corpus size, one could simply take the data from the latest month of recording as proposed by Koehn [50]. This approach would deliver a significant contribution when dealing with recent news analyses, data that is linked to political events or content that changes over time. In the recent case, the topic of scrutiny is multilingual argumentation, which is rather independent from the novelty of events, even if the corpus were more recent than 2011.

Another approach to get rid of irrelevant corpus size is the manual selection of the publicly available official agendas of the European Parliament. What seems promising about this approach is its semantic focus on potentially insightful speeches, yet again, the approach is not automated to a degree to which it creates real usability. However, a semantic selection seems promising, for instance, to use specific competencies of the EU as keywords to identify relevant passages. To empirically identify semantic competencies, keywords are needed that are appearing in the corpus, instead of blindly looking up some terms. Moreover, the set of keywords to be used should be connected to make sure no relevant text is overseen. A group of search terms is needed that accompany each other frequently. A method to identify such patterns is called "*topic modeling*". Its mechanics and implementation are explained in the next section.

3.3.2 Topic Modeling Europarl

The goal of the topic modeling step is to identify semantic content that appears in the Europarl corpus or, to put it simply, to identify what speakers in the European parliament were talking about without having to read 15 years of speeches due to obvious efficiency constraints. Topic modeling is a statistical method to identify semantic patterns in large text collections. The simplest topic modeling algorithm developed by Blei et al. is called "*Latent Dirichlet Allocation*" (LDA) [8] and will be illustrated in the following from a practical perspective. The "*latency*" in the term

Figure 3.2: Probabilistic graphical model for LDA following [8].

results from the assumption that there are several layers of variables, such as words, topics, and documents, whereof the topics are not directly observable and therefore have to be algorithmically inferred. A topic in this context is defined as a distribution of term frequencies over a fixed vocabulary. Figuratively speaking, the topic comprises the semantic dependence of an uttered word on the “*company it keeps*” [77], as for example, the “*blue*” in “*blue sky*” has a different semantic appearance as compared to the same term in “*blue ocean*” or the “*blue light*” of a screen. Since this relation is commutative, meaning “*blue*” frequently co-occurs with “*sky*” and “*sky*” frequently co-occurs with “*blue*”, groups of words that are often found close to each other can be clustered as topics.⁹

The probabilistic assumption the LDA algorithm is built upon implies a text instead of being written or recorded to be randomly drawn from a given vocabulary and topic structure. Figure 3.2 further illustrates the idea in plate notation, a notation representing several instances of a variable by surrounding the variable by a square. $W_{d,n}$, the set of words, is characterized as a dependent, observable variable. $Z_{d,n}$ describes the topic assignment for n_{th} word in the d_{th} document. Both words and assignment function together define the set of topics N . Furthermore, a document D has its own topic proportion it is made of, for instance, a speech comprising the topics of 80% foreign politics, 10% inner politics and 10% comments on the previous speaker, expressed by the variable θ_d . Other than that, there are two hyperparameters α and β . α regulates the smoothing of the per-document topic distribution θ_d , with a high alpha value corresponding to a high similarity between documents and a low α value corresponding to a low similarity between documents. β controls the amount of smoothing of the topic-word distribution over the corpus K . A high β represents a high overlap of words in different topics, whereas a low β implies that words in separated topics are different from each other [85].

The topic modeling is implemented using Python’s gensim library¹⁰ combined with a wrapper to the JAVA-based MALLET tool for fine-tuning [58]. When defining a topic model based on the Europarl corpus, some key factors have to be configured such as the *number of topics* as a typical restriction for clustering algorithms, as well as α and β , represented by the “*optimize_interval*” parameter in gensim. Fur-

⁹As compared to context and attention querying, this approach is not sensitive to word order and not limited to the sentence level.

¹⁰gensim 3.8.3. Last retrieved 02.01.2021 from <https://pypi.org/project/gensim/>

ther factors to increase the model’s usefulness, following Schöch [77], are knowledge of the dataset, knowledge of the topic modeling process itself and the pursuit of a clear research objective. Detailed information on corpus structure can be found in chapter 3.2.3.

The modeling process is conducted in the `run_modeling_process` method. After the preprocessing, described in section 3.3.3, a LdaMallet object controlling the LDA algorithm is called by the optimization method (see 3.3.4) and finally some visualization is executed.

Core to this process is the initiation of the LdaMallet instance to which a total of six parameters is handed. First, the path to the installed mallet binary handling the LDA algorithm is given. Second to be handed is the corpus, a nested list, carrying the documents in Bag-of-Words (BoW) format. Third and fourth, the *number of topics* as well as the number of training iterations are defined. Fifth, a dictionary, the vocabulary, mapping the word IDs to their corresponding string representations is handed over. Finally, to guarantee reproducibility, a fixed random seed is chosen. Given this input, the LdaMallet instance produces a collection of topics and member words. Design decisions are made having in mind the objective to identify common topics in a quantitative manner to reduce the corpus size on a semantic basis.

3.3.3 Preprocessing

Given is the German Europarl in raw UTF-8 format in one piece as it can be downloaded from the Europarl website. The corpus list, made of term-document frequencies as well as the id-to-word-mapping are to be determined in the preprocessing for topic modeling, which are documented below. The preprocessing steps to convert from raw UTF-8 to these two lists are *chunking*, *clean-up*, *stopword removal* and *PoS tagging*. Hence, at first to make sure the spaCy lemmatizer [41] can handle the chunks, which is possible up to a maximum text length of a million characters, the corpus is cut into 679 equally sized snippets of 2500 lines length. Then, special characters and numbers are removed from the text chunks using regular expressions. By the means of the Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK) [7] a set of German stopwords is eliminated. As a stopword is defined as a word being so frequent that it ceases to contribute to an information gain [78], the set of stopwords is extended by the most frequent parliamentary words, identified via the corpus analysis tool Sketch Engine [47]. Such words are for example *„Abgeordneter“* (deputy) or *„Berichterstat-ter“* (correspondent) and their female counterparts. Subsequently, the words are filtered by length using `gensim.utils.preprocessing`. It is assumed that words of a length smaller than 3 chars are too general whereas words of a length greater than 20 chars are too specific, thus carrying no content. To further trim vocabulary size, the tokens are normalized to lowercase and segmented into lemmas of nouns, verbs and adjectives through the German spaCy lemmatizer, since these are the lexical categories known to best capture semantic entities, actions and properties. Finally, the collection of lemmas is transformed to the LDAMallet’s input data using the `gensim.corpora` class.

3.3.4 Hyperparameter Optimization

After the description of preprocessing the topic modeling input, the topic modeling output, or more specifically the optimization of its quality, will be discussed in this section. To verify a topic model’s meaningfulness, common measures are human

Figure 3.4: Coherence value c under "optimize_interval" configurations.

interpretability, evaluation on a labeled classification task or usage of key figures such as coherence values¹¹. The idea of using a coherence value is the approximation of human judgment. As such, coherence measures the degree of semantic similarity between frequent words within a topic. The exact coherence value taken to tune the topic model is c_v , an arithmetic mean of cosine similarity based on context vectors of words and the whole set of words and a sliding window of length 110 to control the document structure. c_v is useful since proven to provide the highest average correlation with human ratings on common corpora [21]. Based on the coherence measure, the *number of topics* has to be optimized and in the aftermath, Mallet's *optimize_interval* variable to determine the adaption of α and β hyperparameters are optimized for c_v .

Figure 3.3: Coherence value c under "number of topic" settings.

On the left side of Figure 3.3, the optimization results for *number of topics* on seven levels, each one separated by steps of 10 (40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90, 100) can be seen computed with 6000 iterations and a random seed of 2. As the c_v has not reached a plateau within the observed interval, additional four levels were scrutinized (110, 120, 130, 140) as depicted on the right side of Figure 3.3. Not depicted is the result of topic numbers larger than 150 which were also tested to exclude a local maximum, but the upward trend of the coherence value is not continued. Consequently, the optimum of coherence is reached for 100 topics with a coherence value of 0.5488.

Figure 3.4 shows the optimization results of the *optimize_interval* variable using

¹¹Evaluate Topic Models. Last retrieved 02.01.2021 from <https://towardsdatascience.com/evaluate-topic-model-in-python-latent-dirichlet-allocation-lda-7d57484bb5d0>

number of topics = 100, again 6000 iterations and a random seed of 2. The observed interval includes a total of five levels (0, 50, 100, 250, 500). According to Mallet’s documentation ¹², the “*option turns on hyperparameter optimization, which allows the model to better fit the data by allowing some topics to be more prominent than others.*” The idea behind this variable springs from a need for different granularity of topics. With Europarl as our object of scrutiny, this could be represented by broad topics containing political jargon or narrow topics, containing only the content of one debate. As the best results are achieved using no hyperparameter optimization at all, it is perceived that an equal partition of topics achieves the best coherence score. This observation confirms the intuition that representative search terms for corpus size reduction should be of average prominence. For these reasons, the final topic model is built with a 100 topics, an *optimize_interval* of 0 and a *coherence score* of 0.5488.

3.3.5 Topic Modeling Results

Of the 100 topics identified from the Europarl corpus for semantic volume limitation, each one was manually named and scored for argumentative potential on a scale between low, middle and high. A collection of all topics and assessments can be found attached to this work.

From an intra-topic perspective, resulting topics and EU competencies can be compared. Regarding hyperparameter granularity, a suitable coverage of the EU’s competences can be confirmed. As can be drawn from Table 3.1, every policy can be assigned to at least one related topic of the topic model. The fields in Table 3.1 are sorted by subsidiary levels.

Figure 3.5: Four randomly drawn example topics in a wordcloud.

¹²Mallet’s parameters. Last retrieved 02.01.2021 from <http://mallet.cs.umass.edu/topics.php>

From the inter-topic perspective, a majority of the topics shows clear, human-interpretable patterns, highlighting either a competence or a specific debate or foreign policy topic. Of course, not every topic is perfectly sharp, as the mediocre height of coherence (0.5488) suggests. Nevertheless, the topic model is sufficient for a preliminary selection of subjects. Figure 3.5 illustrates some example topics in a worldcloud. Accordingly, a topic with clear pro- and counter line was selected for the following step of subcorpus selection, namely the topic of nuclear energy.

Policy	Competence	Related topic
civil defence	members	defence policy, asylum policy, humanitarian aid, justice
education	members	education
culture	members	culture, media
youth	members	drugs and health
sports	members	olympic games
agriculture and fishery	EU and members	agricultural policy, fishery policy, agricultural reforms
education	EU and members	education
energy policy	EU and members	energy policy, nuclear energy, climate crisis
traffic	EU and members	maritime transport, air transport, mobility, traffic
environmental policy	EU and members	health, hazardous substances, forestry, environmental guidelines, protection of animals, waste disposal
research and development	EU and members	research and ethics, research and development, organ donation, medicine
consumer protection	EU and members	food labelling, consumer protection and trade, food safety, genetic engineering, medicinal products
security and defence policy	eu and members	data security, europol
social policy	EU and members	human rights, equal rights, family, collaboration, aid for disaster victims
customs union	EU	fiscal policy
fair trading	EU	competition policy, economic policy
monetary policy	EU	finance, financial crisis, economy, euro
foreign trade policy	EU	globalization, russia, turkey, u.s., international trade, international treaties

Table 3.1: Subdomains of the EU and their corresponding topics.

3.3.6 Extraction of Subcorpus

From the topic model of Europarl the topic entitled "*nuclear energy*" is picked to define a set of search terms. These terms are next to be used to extract a smaller annotation corpus.

First and foremost, irrelevant documents are filtered out. A document is not relevant if it does not contain any of the search terms. The applied search terms for the German corpus are: "*nuklear*" (nuclear), "*kernenergie*" (nuclear energy), "*radioaktiv*" (radioactive), "*kernkraftwerk*" (nuclear power plant), and "*reaktor*" (reactor). The exact translations were used for the French corpus ("*nucléaire*", "*énergie nucléaire*", "*radioactive*", "*radioactif*", "*centrale nucléaire*", "*réacteur*"), with the peculiarity that for the adjective "*radioaktiv*", translations in both genders need to be included, meaning "*radioactif*" and "*radioactive*".

In the next step, the documents containing whole sessions must be split up due to the level of speeches, which is of interest. To execute this cut, the XML tag `<speaker>` is exploited to identify search terms within a speech. Once the relevant speeches are found, they are cleared from XML tags and additional information before the form of address, so that they are in pure text format. Note that in the French version of the corpus some ligatures in files before the v3 release from 2003 are not correctly shown. For instance, in a speech given in 2002, the French word for heart "*cœur*" would appear as "*cur*" in the transcripts. The circumstances were solved through the introduction of UTF-8 encoding. In this subcorpus, the affected words are left unchanged for transparency reasons.

Having extracted and cleaned the content of speech nodes, some unwanted documents still remain. Not every record from the European Parliament automatically contains a speech. Frequently, simple interjections or organizational remarks occur. Those are handled consequently by a length-of-speech filter that excludes every file smaller than 8 KB. The sum of reduction measures results in 242 speeches per language. To achieve the temporally reasonable objective of 60 speeches per language, a random sample is drawn of the remaining speeches.

3.4 ADU Annotation

Having extracted a topic-based data sample from the Europarl corpus, the next task comprises the creation of human-made labels, the annotation. In the annotation step, trained human experts are asked to assess whether a sentence is part of an ADU or not and if so, whether a sentence belongs to a claim or a premise. One single person cannot solve this task alone. In order to resolve ambiguity, two measures of quality control serve as indispensable pillars: domain expertise and communication. Janier et al. [43] summarize some aspects for an effective annotation quality control: "accuracy", "stability", "reproducibility", "granularity", "scope" and "ambiguity". "Accuracy", "stability" and "reproducibility" will be addressed in section 3.4.5 through the measurement of inter-annotator agreement (IAA). To guarantee the "accuracy" standard, guidelines need to be established ex ante (see section 3.4.3) additional to the analysis of the results ex post (see section 3.4.5). "Stability" describes the agreement of an annotator with himself over time or in this case the agreement of an annotator having scrutinized two translations of one speech in different languages. In a similar manner, "reproducibility" is achieved through the measurement of agreement between the annotators. The appropriate "granularity" of the annotation model will be discussed in section 3.4.2, dealing with the annotation scheme. Furthermore, the annotation needs to follow a clear "scope" and should lead to minimal "ambiguity". Therefore, the annotators are provided with clear definitions and basic decision rules, which will be further explained in the guidelines section 3.4.3.

3.4.1 Annotation Process

The overall annotation process is organized in two phases. Phase one is a preliminary study to develop some guidelines. One annotator works on a total of 120 speeches. Thereof, 60 translations are in German, another 60 translations are in French. In the second annotation round the speeches are split up in bundles of 15, each assigned to an annotator executing a second, independent assessment of the speeches. Ergo, as a result, there are two annotations per speech-language pair and every session is evaluated by three annotators, namely the first annotator in French and German, the second annotator for the French version, and the second annotator for the German version. This allows it to consolidate possible discrepancies in the aftermath by majority voting. Figure 3.6 illustrates this structure. Compared to other annotation studies, the allocation of workload is rather centralized, yet the task is solved collaboratively. The bundles' size of 15 for the second annotation phase can be handled in approximately one day of work, enough to allow the annotator to have a learning curve in handling the speeches.

Figure 3.6: Centrally vs. decentrally organized annotation process.

Regarding the annotators' domain expertise and background, nine students were involved in the task. Five of the students are enrolled in business informatics, two in translation and one in political science. Each one confirmed to have worked with scientific texts before. Seven of the annotators are native speakers in the language they do the annotation work in, five German natives and two French natives. The remaining two annotators have a language level of B2-C1 according to the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR), indicating the ability to "read complex reports, analyses and commentaries where opinions, viewpoints and connections are discussed."¹³ The annotators were trained on annotation examples in the guidelines and difficult cases were discussed in online meetings.

Technically, the annotation was executed using the brat annotation tool [84], a web tool often used in related studies [43], which can be found at ¹⁴. Brat allows hosting own annotation projects using a self-defined annotation scheme, thus enabling flexibility and extensibility. Through configurable shortcuts and an intuitive graphical user interface (GUI), it is easy to use. According to the annotation scheme, annotators can mark text spans and connect them through defined n-ary relations. Considerations on the annotation scheme will be treated in the next chapter. Moreover, brat also delivers some useful functions to compare annotations of the same file and practical links to dictionaries or wikis. It uses its own output format ".ann", which is text-based and easy to parse for further processing.

3.4.2 Annotation Scheme

There are many different approaches to annotate arguments, some of which are summarized in Table 3.2 following [83]. Peldszus and Stede[66] define in their micro text scheme a simple claim-rooted tree structure based on Freeman's argumentation theory. Text segments on the nodes on subsentence level are connected through the relations "support", "linked support", "rebuttal" and "undercutting". Very related to that, Stab and Gurevych [82] introduce their annotation scheme for persuasive essays, which also spans a tree over subsentence fragments connected through "support" and "attack" relations. Targeting the domain of scientific papers, Kirschner et al. [49] present a graph-based scheme on sentence level, relinquishing roles and tree structure. The sentences are linked through the labeled edges "support", "attack", "sequence", and "detail". Interestingly, both "sequence" from the science scheme and "linked support" from the micro text scheme assume that support can emerge from combined text segments. Furthermore, Habernal and Gurevych [35] create a modified Toulmin scheme for web discourse, generalizing Toulmin's work for realistic scenarios. Opposite to the previous schemes, they relinquish relations, assuming that the role of an ADU is entirely defined by its position in the representation structure. Hence, the labels "claim", "premise", "rebuttal" and "refutation" are used. To conclude this short literature inspection, Niculae et al. [63] criticize the commonly used tree structures in the domain of online forums, since 28% of comments in their study are not linked at all. In their eRulemaking scheme, they apply a different graph model based on "policy", "value", "fact" and "reference" nodes as well as "evidence" and "reason" relations. The annotation approaches differ in their domains, whereof some are web-related whereas others follow well-defined writing

¹³CEFR. Last retrieved 02.02.2021 from

<https://www.coe.int/en/web/common-european-framework-reference-languages/level-descriptions>

¹⁴brat annotation tool. Last retrieved 02.02.2021 from <https://brat.nlplab.org/>

Paper	Domain	Structure	Level
Peldszus and Stede 2014	microtexts	tree	subsentence
Stab and Gurevych 2014	persuasive essays	tree	subsentence
Kirschner et al. 2015	scientific papers	graph	sentence
Habernal and Gurevych 2017	web discourse	set	supersentence
Niculae et al. 2017	eRulemaking online forum	graph	subsentence

Table 3.2: Different annotation scheme approaches.

rules. They differ in granularity between subsentence and supersentence level and finally in their datastructures such as trees, graphs and sets being controversial. As a consequence, the annotation scheme drawn up for this work can be distinguished from the others through its domain, structure and granularity. The domain is set to political debates in the Europarl subcorpus (compare 3.2.4). Following the recent trend in NLP to keep the preprocessing simple and let the LM grasp the linguistic complexity ¹⁵, the choice of a clean and simplistic model is made. The common ground of the above-described structures lies in the distinction between claims and premises. Thus, simple, flat labeling of claims and premises is implemented in this work.

After the choice for political domain and flat structure of the annotation scheme, the granularity must be determined. Here, the decision is made in favor of sentence level. First, both languages follow an easily detectable sentence structure. Second, the domain of political speeches is formal. Using a legal register, premises and claims should be found in different sentences 2.2.2. Attaching an ADU to a sentence is a simplification. Obviously, a claim could be longer or shorter than one sentence, for instance in a causal clause. However, training data has to be handed over to a model in a unified way and the role of the sentence surrounding a word is crucial for the LM's performance. Therefore, annotations are made on sentence level. In literature, considerations on granularity are not in the focus of interest, leaving room for improvement since explicit design choices are more transparent than implicit.

¹⁵Norvig-Chomsky debate. Last retrieved 02.02.2021 from <https://norvig.com/chomsky.html>

Figure 3.7: Annotation scheme in UML and implementation in Brat.

Given the design considerations discussed above, Figure 3.7 illustrates how the scheme is implemented. An ADU can either be a claim or a premise. The text span of every two ADUs is disjoint as is declared in the brat-configuration file, shown in the bottom-left area of Figure 3.7. ADUs and arguments as their composition are implicitly implemented through claims and premises and their quantity, thus, the abstract marker “!” is set. In particular, an argument consists of at least one claim and at least one premise because a claim without reasoning can only be a non-argumentative statement and a premise without a claim is a fatherless child. This leaves three options open for sentence classification. A sentence can either be a claim, a premise or not argumentative at all. This definition leads to some necessary decision rules developed and communicated in the guidelines (see 3.4.3). It is important to distinguish between the “*sentence-claim*” relation and “*sentence-premise*” relation. As an argument contains exactly one claim serving as its main message, comparably to a primary key in relation databases, the association between sentence and claim is interchangeable. Premises, on the other hand, are subordinate to the argument itself, as it is expressed by the tree structures from the literature. Consequently, sentences and premises share a “*part-of*” relation, meaning that one sentence can be part of one premise and one premise consists of at least one sentence in this simplified argumentation scheme.

3.4.3 Annotation Guidelines

The annotation scheme is translated to gold standard data by annotators as described in the sections above. How the annotators are instructed is the topic of the following section. In the first annotation round conducted by the main annotator, guidelines were developed to anchor shared tutorials and working definitions. The annotators were given some context to the task, the background on claims and premises and some visual examples either in French or in German. Additionally, they received a quick tour through the usage of the annotation tool and instructions regarding the workflow and best practices. All of these can be found in the files handed in with the thesis.

Figure 3.8 shows the annotation workflow, which an annotator must follow through the speeches in a top-down approach. At first, the dedicated speech has to be skimmed over to understand the speech’s context. This step is mostly obvious, yet necessary in case the speech is extracted as a follow-up speech in the scope of a long debate in the parliament. Then, the annotator should go over the speech paragraph by paragraph. The paragraphs are kept from the original corpus version for assistance reasons. Paragraph and argument structures are correlated except for some cases where the translator-made paragraphs derive from the original speaker’s choice. Analyzing a paragraph, the annotator must decide whether the text is argumentative at all, thereby excluding welcomes, farewells, acknowledgments and descriptive language. If a paragraph is found to be argumentative, a sentence has to be marked as the claim. Following the claim, one or more premises have to be identified. Inspired by the valuable guidelines produced by Stab and Gurevych [82], some typical claim and premise indicators were enumerated to the annotators as a checklist. Typical claim indicators are “*consequently*” or “*in my opinion*”, typical premise indicators are “*as the example illustrates*” or “*moreover*”.

Figure 3.8: Top-down workflow.

3.4.4 Preliminary Study

Further, the last section of the guidelines highlighted some peculiarities, which arose in the preliminary study and some best practices to cope with them. Some passages are recognizable for the political domain, leaving some room for interpretation. Figure 3.9 gives an example of a such difficulty, namely implicit claims and premises. The extract contains clauses talking about reasons to accept a request but only gives them in a descriptive way using relative clauses. In the guidelines, annotators are advised to discover argumentative style only. This means a passage as presented in Figure 3.9 will not be identified as argumentative due to non-fulfilled stylistic

Figure 3.9: Usage of neutral clauses instead of argumentative premises.

criteria. This issue is also related to the use of indirect speech, past tenses and subjunctive mood, and argumentative style. In the aftermath, the rule implies an approved loss of recall in the identification of arguments or, to put it simply, not every argument can be found.

Another area dealing with implicit semantic is the interpretation of premises. It is unclear how far the support of a claim goes. Some supporting sentences such as the rebuttal of a counterargument are indirect or not rationally founded. In political speeches, rhetorical devices such as repetitions, rhetorical questions or correctios are frequent to convince the audience. This peculiarity is solved through the annotation rule determining a premise to specify, justify or highlight the importance. Highlighting importance does not have to be achieved by rational means – it can also be achieved rhetorically. No rule comes without an exception: if the claim of an argument is the importance of a message, the sentence highlighting importance could also serve as the claim.

Moreover, the speaker’s stance or intention plays a major role in the annotation. In other words, the annotator has to pay attention to whether the speaker is arguing in favor or against a topic to correctly identify ADUs. Usually, in the Europarl corpus, the speaker aims at a defined action or acceptance of the audience. Hence, the speaker justifies some action. However, in cases of ambiguity such as the implicit claims described above, identifying the intended action requires reading between the lines. An example is given in Figure 3.10, where the speaker’s stance is relevant for the distinction between claim and rebuttal-premise. As a consequence, human annotators who are made aware of this context should be capable to reach a consensus. It will be interesting to see whether LMs can reliably grasp this form of context.

Figure 3.10: Claim identification depends on the stance.

In section 3.4.3 claim and premise indicators were introduced, small conjunctions that help to identify a claim or a premise as such, which could be easily found by a regex search. Although these indicators are nice to have to develop some expertise in spotting an argument, they can also lead to false positives. In this manner, several “because” occur that are not expressing evidence, misleading the unpracticed annotator.

Figure 3.11: An enumeration of high-level arguments.

Further, some arguments are not formulated formally, e.g. two ADUs could be connected by an *and*. This enumerative style also touches the domain of enumerated claims and the level of abstraction real-world arguments are using, not necessarily following the structure defined in this study. Figure 3.11 contains an example of a very high-level speech, touching several areas with just a few references.

In case an ADU does not fit into a sentence, because it is too long or too short respectively, annotators were handed a set of rules to decide systematically. Note that if claims and premises are contained in the same sentence, the sentence has to be marked as claim due to the claim’s defining function of the argument itself. If several claim candidates are found in the paragraph, the annotators are advised to follow the inference chain by inserting a consecutive conjunction such as *thus* into the candidate sentence, identifying the sentence as logically inferred if the sentence’s meaning does not change. The last case includes two claim candidates with similar content. In this context, a blue-pencil test is to be applied to determine which of the sentences could be left out without changing the message to evaluate importance.

3.4.5 Inter-Annotator Agreement Analysis

Having started with the annotation process, scheme and guidelines to minimize the task’s subjectivity, then moved to peculiarities and difficulties still inherent, we now close the chapter by assessing their interplay incorporated by the annotation’s degree of maturity. The metrics to address this issue measure Inter-Annotator Agreement (IAA) as well as Intra-Annotator Agreement, serving to guarantee the corpus’s accuracy. The IAA measures, how well a number of annotators make the same annotation decision for a certain category. Thus, it directly reflects the quality of the guidelines and the difficulty of the task. If IAA is high, the annotation is labeled as reproducible following Janier et al. [43]. The Intra-Annotator Agreement, however, describes the extent to which the same annotator produces the same classification, be it over time or in this case over different languages. Janier calls this agreement the stability of the annotation. In the context of ambiguous linguistic data, full stability of the annotation can be aimed at but for sure never achieved.

The aggregated labels from the annotation phase are collected in a comma-separated value (CSV) file to subsequently compute the IAA. During the annotation step using the brat tool, claims and premises were labeled on a sentence basis. Since the corpus also encompasses non-argumentative passages, which were not explicitly marked in the original annotation phase, the additional label *NoAdu* is introduced for the consolidated master annotation, where conflicts are resolved. Therefore, each sentence is guaranteed to be classified as exactly one of the classes *Claim*, *Premise* or *NoAdu*. If first and second annotators disagreed on the argumentative quality of a sentence, the disaccord was resolved through a comparison with the sentence’s

translated version as long as the argument was still coherent after the edit. In the rare event the argument's coherence was not given, for instance, two annotators disagree which sentence of a paragraph best captures the argument's claim with the respective third annotator also disagreeing, the individual case was decided by inclusion of the guidelines (e.g. the last possible claim was picked according to the decision rules).

The German corpus version comprises 4343 sentences. The French version comprises 4328 sentences. The numbers are similar, yet not identical, because the French version forms longer sentences in some rare cases. Thereof, 2728 identical sentences are identified as argumentative and 1327 are identified as non-argumentative for the German data. Note that these numbers do not add up to the total number of sentences due to controversial passages.

Figure 3.12: The present paragraph could be seen as argumentative or not.

An exemplary paragraph which cannot be clearly decided to be argumentative is depicted in Figure 3.12. In paragraph 22 of the speech "ep-04-09-14-s78", the speaker highlights why he is avoiding a contentious issue, giving reasons for this decision. The paragraph is unclear since it could be interpreted as an organizational remark on one hand, but on the other hand, the defined claim and premise structure could be recognized. As a result of the majority vote, the paragraph was decided to count as argumentative in the master annotation. In this regard, note that due to the corpus's real-world origin, although the majority of speeches contain argumentative content, there is also a considerable amount of text identified as non-argumentative. For instance, speech "ep-02-05-14-s187" contains no single argument that the annotators agreed on. The speech is still an invaluable contribution to the corpus as it shows there is no lower limit on arguments for each speech, thus a set entirely composed of "NoAdu" labels is perfectly possible. For a paragraph, having a substantial argumentative quality is necessary yet not sufficient to determine the distribution of its incorporated sentences to claims and premises.

Of the 727 claims identified by the first annotator, 604 were agreed upon on the German dataset, equaling 83,08% of the observed agreement for claims. This percentage shows, that the difficulties elaborated in the preliminary studies could be decreased, meaning the identification of the argumentative line of a paragraph was clear to the annotators in most cases. An example of disagreement regarding a paragraph's claim can be found in Figure 3.13., with one sentence containing the claim indicator "therefore" and the other one containing the intention to act. In the consolidated version, the latter was decided to be the claim in agreement with the French annotation.

Natürlich bin ich mir der Tatsache bewusst, dass für die CCS-Technologie noch eine umfangreiche Forschungstätigkeit erforderlich sein wird, bevor sie kommerziell einsatzfähig ist.

Deshalb wird CCS im Strategieplan für Energietechnologie als strategische Energietechnologie aufgenommen. Das ist auch der Grund, weshalb wir diese Technologie in Verbindung mit dem Legislativvorschlag zum Gegenstand einer Mitteilung machen werden.

Figure 3.13: Controversial claims.

Similarly, 1905 of the 2106 premises of the first annotator reached agreement on the German dataset, equaling to 90,46% of the observed agreement. It is noticeable that the arguments' borders in particular are difficult to identify, as annotators have to decide where exactly the support of an argument ends, as the example in Figure 3.14 illustrates. In this manner, paragraph seven in speech "ep-00-11-15_s251" opens with a context-giving sentence. This can be interpreted as non-argumentative transition or as the first premise of the argument. Consolidation treated the sentence as a premise since two annotators found it to highlight the importance of the claim. Other than that, it can be questionable, whether or not premises always have to be adjacent or whether or not they can stretch out to other paragraphs.

Als zweite Frage ist die Versorgungssicherheit ein Schlüsselement zur Gewährleistung der wirtschaftlichen Entwicklung, des Wohlstands unserer Länder und der Europäischen Union als Ganzes.

Es muss über die Rolle gesprochen werden, die die einzelnen Energiequellen in diesem Buch spielen müssen. An erster Stelle ist da die Energieeinsparung.

Figure 3.14: Treatment of context-giving sentence.

Regarding the counting method, the sentence labels of the first and second annotator were compared to each other and counted up in case they have matched. Hence, if one paragraph was found to be argumentative by both annotators without them agreeing on the paragraph's claim, not only the number of identical claims does not increase, but also the number of identical premises is not counting up because the other annotator would turn the alleged premise into a claim in his annotation. As the total number of premises of the corpus exceeds the number of claims, this effect is of lower importance for the observed premise agreement.

Besides this dependence of claims and premises and argumentative text passages and their different frequencies, the pure observed agreement on a label as the percentage of annotations on which the annotators agree [43] seems biased and therefore unsuitable. Due to these reasons the IAA metric to be scrutinized is Cohen's κ [16]. The metric is computed by formula 3.1.

$$\kappa = \frac{Pr(a) - Pr(e)}{1 - Pr(e)} \quad (3.1)$$

The κ 's numerator captures the deviance between relative observed agreements over all labels and agreement by chance taking into account how often each annotator selects each label. The denominator contains a shortened normalization over sentence length and agreement by chance. As compared to the measure of observed agreement, Cohen's κ adjusts the total frequencies by base probabilities of the labels and agreement by chance. The reason why Cohen's κ was used instead of the more

<i>German annotator 0</i>	<i>German annotator 1-4</i>			
	# NoAdu	# Claim	# Premise	<i>row total</i>
# NoAdu	1327			1510
# Claim		604		727
# Premise			1905	2106
<i>column total</i>	1447	755	2141	4343

Table 3.3: Contingency table for German annotations.

general Fleiss κ lies within the annotation’s document structure. On each document, two annotators have worked, hence, the simple metric was computed. Table 3.3 is a German contingency table, showing the number of labels given by the annotators and their intersections. The reproducibility of the German corpus sums up to a Cohen’s κ of 0,81. According to Landis and Koch [51], an agreement measure of over 80% is categorized as the highest achievable threshold.

Nevertheless, interpreting this value highly depends on the task at hand. A 0,81 agreement for a PoS-tagging task would be considered a failure, whereas, for manual ADU detection, it is a promising result. The value was probably enabled through the strongly simplifying assumptions of only two to three labels, the modeling of part-of-relations between sentences and ADUs, and the presence of parsed coherent paragraphs in the Europarl corpus. The guidelines, containing an annotation process as well as decision rules and the possibility for discussion during the annotation also helped in reaching a high IAA. However, in doing so it was possible to eliminate a huge part of the subjectivity and finally accomplish a solid consensus.

<i>French annotator 0</i>	<i>French annotator 1-4</i>			
	# NoAdu	# Claim	# Premise	<i>row total</i>
# NoAdu	1251			1492
# Claim		606		710
# Premise			1862	2126
<i>column total</i>	1425	781	2122	4328

Table 3.4: Contingency table for French annotations.

The French corpus attains a Cohen’s κ of 0,77, an agreement categorized as “*substantial*” by Landis and Koch [51]. Find the underlying values in the French contingency Table 3.4. As can be seen, this κ diverges from the German corpus by approximately 0.4%, even scoring in a weaker threshold. Although a substantial agreement can be assessed as a positive result and the German and French κ values are in the same scope, they are not identical. Reasons for this may be found in different annotators’ perceptions in general, which could only be solved by scale or in the lacking availability of French natives. Other than that, the annotation process was the same for both datasets and the appropriate gold standard for further processing could be set. The overall IAA comprises a Cohen’s κ of 0,79.

Moreover, the Intra-Annotator Agreement was computed using Cohen’s κ . As the annotation process was organized centrally, having one annotator working on both translated sets of speeches, it was also possible to measure the stability of annotation for this annotator to further have an intuition on annotation security and the influence of randomness on the annotation. With Cohen’s κ of 0.93, the annotation

shows itself as very consistent. As one might assume, this value proved to be higher than the corresponding Inter-Annotator measurements.

To summarize, the quality of the bilingual corpus could be validated through measurement of both Inter-Annotator Agreement and Intra-Annotator Agreement. The measurement of Cohen's κ , chosen for its simple design, yet clean setup regarding the coincidental agreement, delivered substantial results of 0,81 for the German corpus, 0,79 for the French corpus and 0,79 overall. The annotation's stability and reproducibility are very good, indicating sufficient handling of peculiarities of the task. Differences caused by remaining subjectivity were consolidated by the use of majority voting, then inserted in the master annotation. Although the results of the French corpus are slightly worse than those of the German corpus, they are well-suited for further processing. Annotation raw data, accumulated tables and guidelines are handed over with this work.

3.5 Further Preprocessing

For the transition from annotated text data to the final LM input, some file reading and syntactic harmonization have to be executed. The bilingual ADU detection sub-corpus transforms over four file formats during the project proceedings. Figure 3.15 pre shows its transition from XML, over ANN and CSV to the pandas DataFrame expected by the LMs. To give a short recap of chapter 3.3.6, during data sampling, the relevant speeches are filtered out by bilingual search terms on the XML version of Europarl. The speaker tags in the XML tree can be used to determine start and end of the speeches and the paragraph tags are replaced by simple linebreaks, a piece of useful information for speech structure for the following annotation step. This way, 120 files could be distilled, each one titled by the session day and the speaker ID.

The cleaned XML files were then distributed under the annotators through the brat annotation tool. After the annotations were made, the master annotation was formed, from which the tool automatically generated annotation files in its homebrew format “.ann”. The 120 Annotation files are simple textfiles following a tab-separated structure $\langle ID \rangle$, $\langle start\ position \rangle$, $\langle end\ position \rangle$, $\langle label \rangle$, $\langle sentence \rangle$. The first item in each line is a metadata ID, built by the letter “T” and a running number, the annotation metadata are sorted by creation, not by position in the document. To capture this information, the start and end indices of the sequence in the text are given, this information matters particularly to free sequence annotation. However, due to the clear sentence annotation instruction, the positions are not necessary for further processing. After the positions follows the label of each annotation entry. The labels provided are *NoAdu*, *Claim* and *Premise* so that $s \in \{NoAdu, Claim, Premise\}$, whereby $NoAdu \cap Claim \cap Premise = \emptyset$. The final component of each line is the sentence itself. Some lines contain annotators’ comments.

Figure 3.15: File formats during preprocessing.

Given the 120 .ANN files on speech-level, the speeches are appended to one joined file using Python’s pandas library [89]. The non-used attributes such as IDs and positions are eliminated by just reading in the relevant columns. The encoding of the resulting CSV file is set to UTF-8 to deal with the French symbols. Another change, required by the LMs for the subsequent ADU detection task, is the transformation of the labels from textual to numerical data. Thus, *NoAdu* is mapped to zero, *Claim* is mapped to one and *Premise* is mapped to two. The final format of the CSV file is a $\langle text \rangle$ column followed by a numerical $\langle label \rangle$. This last step has to be performed three times, to build one dataset for German, one dataset for French and one concatenated bilingual dataset.

Finally, the three CSV files are read into pandas.DataFrames. A training split of 90% of the randomly shuffled entries is then given to the LMs as the experiments’ input data.

3.6 ADU Detection Models

In the following chapter, the selection and composition of the LMs to be evaluated in the ADU detection experiments will be presented. In order to provide systematic information, chapter 3.6.1 explains the selection criteria, under which the five LMs were identified. Subsequently, chapters 3.6.2 to 3.6.5 introduce the accordingly chosen LMs German BERT, CamemBERT, mBERT, DistilBert German and DistilBert Multilingual.

3.6.1 Selection Criteria

Well-defined selection criteria to determine the observed LMs are of particular importance, since a representative sample is needed to make valid statements on the state of the art for the ADU detection in the target languages. Therefore, it is not only necessary to systematically identify the experiment's object, but also to systematically describe how the models differentiate methodically. Some key aspects to consider are choice of LMs in general, availability, resources, pretraining objective, feature level and multilingualism.

Choice of LMs. Inspired by the state-of-the-art results in NLP of transfer learning approaches based on the Transformer architecture as described in chapter 2.3.2, the choice in favor of LMs is an obvious one. Pretrained LMs outperform prehistorically used LSTM architectures due to their far enhanced accuracy. Since LMs receive a lot of attention, suitable LMs have to be chosen for the ADU classification in a political domain in two languages. The next two criteria consulted in the LM selection are of economic nature: availability and resources.

Availability. Availability describes that LMs are freely available for download and academic work. As the NLP community is eager to cross-pollinate and democratize their tools, there is an abundance of free-to-use LMs to be found online. A widely used repository hosting both PyTorch and TensorFlow implementations of common LMs is the Hugging Face repository [102]. As the collection found on Hugging Face is voluminous and easy to use, all LMs were downloaded from this source.

Resources. The second economic criterion "*resources*" concerns an elementary architecture choice in LMs. Starting from BERT [20], LMs tend to come in two sizes: "*base*" and "*large*". The base architecture is the standard architecture as conceptually used for BERT's pretraining, whereas the large architecture should lead the transformer up to its full potential. Size-induced performance improvements are to be expected but cannot be exploited working with a conventional student pc, they must be controlled for. Consequently, the focus of this work is set solely on the "*base*" version of each LM. As most recent LMs provide a "*base*" version, this decision comes with the inherent side effect of invaluable comparability. The choice in favor of the "*base*" version of each LM profits from the previously outlined choice in favor of transfer-learning-based LMs because the training effort is shifted on to the external pretraining, making the LM usage economically attractive.

Pretraining Objective. Next, some criteria regarding pretraining will be illustrated. LMs are the results of their corresponding workflows, each one designed for a certain purpose. This purpose may include NLP tasks as different as PoS tagging and Question Answering, different domains or different syntactical levels. A key factor to keep in mind when selecting a model is hence an appropriate pretraining objective. The ADU task at hand requires some knowledge on the relation between sentences as the order of sentences is a rudimentary part of argument structures. It is to be assumed that LMs such as BERT pretrained on an NSP task should have such a level of knowledge encoded. If the chosen LM has been pretrained on an NSP task, this is considered an advantage.

Feature Level. Moreover, the LMs should be based on the same feature level. Every LM should be able to handle sentences as input data. The maximal number of input token length should be configurable and the pretraining tasks should contain text-span-based classification tasks as mentioned before. However, this requirement is a soft constraint since it can be alleviated through preprocessing and tuning, for instance through padding, meaning filling up optional empty tokens with placeholders.

Multilingualism. The last criterion taken into account in the domain of pretraining is multilingualism. In this regard, monolingual models and multilingual models are distinguishable. In this case, monolingual models are pretrained on data encoded in one language that is either German or French. A multilingual model is trained on a set of two or more languages, in the context of this work including German and French. Representatives of both model types will be scrutinized. Two German monolingual models, one French monolingual model and two multilingual versions of BERT. Both approaches promise insightful results as monolingual models could be superiorly crafted to the task, whereas multilingual models could be leveraged through shared properties between languages and scale. The following chapter illustrates the five LMs in further detail.

3.6.2 German BERT

The first LM chosen is German BERT created by deepset ¹⁶. Similar to its English predecessor, the monolingual model has 12 layers, the number of hidden states comes to 768 and a total of 12 attention heads is used. The German BERT comprises 110 million parameters. As the name suggests, German BERT is pretrained on German text data originating in the German Wikipedia, OpenLegalData and news articles. The cleaned data chunks were segmented into sentences with spacy v2.1 and tokenized using SentencePiece. The tokenization is fine-tuned for the German language by producing larger tokens as illustrated on the German BERT website, where an example tokenization of the German word “Ärzte” (doctors) is given to illustrate the semantically meaningful tokens as shown in Figure 3.16.

¹⁶bert-base-german-cased. Last retrieved 02.01.2021 from <https://deepset.ai/german-bert>

Figure 3.16: Example of tokenization used for German BERT by deepset.

Pretraining tasks for German BERT were classical MLM and NSP. In the masked language modeling task, the tokens are covered by a masked token with a probability of 0.8, otherwise replaced by a random token with a probability of 0.1 or left unchanged with a probability of 0.1. The content of the mask token has to be predicted. The second pretraining task used to create German BERT is NSP, a task where the model is supposed to predict whether two sentences attached to each other and separated by a <sep> token are consecutive or not. Although the amount of pretraining data is rather small with a size of 12 GB, the model delivers state-of-the-art results in the domain of identification of offensive language, named entity recognition (NER) and document classification.

3.6.3 CamemBERT

Representative for the state of the art in French monolingual LM is CamemBERT. This section describes the CamemBERT language model, developed by Facebook AI Research and the Sorbonne University in Paris [56]. CamemBERT is a wrapper around Facebook AI’s RoBERTa using the same set of key hyperparameters for pretraining, such as larger mini-batches and learning rates as compared to BERT¹⁷. Also differently to BERT is CamemBERT’s architecture. CamemBERT implements whole-word masking as its MLM strategy indicating that whole words instead of word parts are the prediction target. A peculiarity of CamemBERT is its input data assembly. The corpus selection of CamemBERT relies on the principles of volume, diversity and generality. The volume of CamemBERT far exceeds the one of German BERT with 138 GB of pretraining data. As can be deduced from the corpus’ size, its composition is not entirely homogenous, resulting in the model’s diversity aspect. The pretraining is robust due to the usage of the preclassified and prefiltered OSCAR corpus, a CommonCrawl snapshot from 2018, UTF-8 normalized in French. Thus, the effectiveness of CamemBERT’s diverse pretraining could be shown through the evaluation on four different NLP tasks, namely PoS tagging, dependency parsing, natural language inference (NLI) and NER. CamemBERT’s generality originates in being trained on sources other than Wikipedia. The tokenizer used for CamemBERT is SentencePiece, which generated a vocabulary of 32.000 subword tokens. The model’s size comprises 110 million parameters. The other popular French LM FlauBERT [52] and the multilingual XLM-RoBERTa [17] were also tested for the experiments but had to be excluded due to the resource criterion.

¹⁷CamemBERT description in Hugging Face. Last retrieved 02.01.2021 from https://huggingface.co/transformers/model_doc/camembert.html

3.6.4 mBert

The BERT release mBERT stands for multilingual BERT as the LM is trained on a total of 104 languages. It follows the BERT model architecture and training method, hence it is trained on both, an MLM task and an NSP task, which perfectly qualifies the model for the experiments [20]. mBERT was pretrained on 57 GB of concatenated multilingual Wikipedia data. Different data volumes of the multilingual Wikipedia versions were brought into line through over- and undersampling proportional to available training data sizes. As the first real multilingual model, mBERT reduced the need for cross-lingual supervision as compared to explicit mappings between parallel corpora through zero-shot cross-lingual transfer. This idea behind zero-shot cross-lingual transfer is to carry out “*transfer learning with different source and target domain*” [103]. Thus, knowledge from a high-resource source language can be profitably applied to a low-resource target language as there are shared words and properties. mBERT is built upon WordPiece tokenization. It has a multilingual vocabulary size of 110.000 subword tokens. Shared subword tokens between languages are shown to correlate with positive transfer performance. Additionally, the fine-tuning of mBERT revealed that freezing the transformer’s bottom layers, presumably containing more general knowledge shared among various languages, led to performance gains. With a volume of 179 million parameters, the model is one of the largest LMs applied in these experiments. mBERT is evaluated over five NLP tasks: NLI, document classification, NER, PoS tagging and dependency parsing, most of which have German test sets but three have French test sets. Overall, mBERT proves itself effective and outperforms cross-lingual embeddings.

3.6.5 DistilBERT

The DistilBERT model from Hugging Face is a further development of BERT, trained for usage under constrained computational possibilities [76]. DistilBERT shares the same base architecture as BERT with six layers and 12 attention heads but is 40% smaller and 60% faster. With an accuracy of 97% of BERT, the smaller version is very efficient, which makes it suitable for the ADU experiments. The LM was pretrained using knowledge distillation, where a student model is taught by a teacher model to reproduce its behavior in a cost-saving manner. Thus, compared to BERT, the number of hidden layers is halved. As DistilBERT was created focusing pretraining efficiency instead of a downstream task, several downstream versions of DistilBERT are available. Chosen for the experiments are `distilbert-base-german-cased` as the second German LM and `distilbert-multilingual-cased` as the second multilingual LM. The DistilBERTs share the same training data with their large counterparts. Multilingual DistilBERT has a total of 134 million parameters and German DistilBERT has a total of 66 million parameters ¹⁸.

¹⁸Hugging Face pretrained models. Last retrieved 02.02.2021 from https://huggingface.co/transformers/pretrained_models.html

3.7 ADU Detection Experiments and Tuning

The five pretrained LMs are trained for the downstream task. The training of an already pretrained model is also called tuning. The downstream task consists of a sentence classification task, tailored to ADUs, the ADU detection. Each LM is treated uniformly in an experimental environment. The five LMs perform the ADU detection task, while some parameters are tuned. The best chosen configuration of each model is then considered in the experiments. After the description of the used hardware environment 3.7.1, the experiments' code is summarized 3.7.2, followed by the set model parameters 3.7.3. The most important parameters are then optimized with the ADAM optimizer in chapter 3.7.4 and 3.7.5.

3.7.1 Hardware Environment

At first, the hardware environment for the experiments is pointed out. Due to the advances in language modeling, tasks that used to take days to perform can now be performed in hours or minutes, even on a home computer. Taking advantage of these developments, this thesis's experiments are conducted on a home machine. The experiments are run on an 8-Core Windows 10 Pro machine. Furthermore, the working memory is 31.9 GB RAM. To accelerate matrix multiplications and parallel computations, the NVIDIA CUDA toolkit was used on a NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2070 SUPER GPU with 8 GB GDDR6. Under several runs of the LMs, each model's best configuration was determined and executed on the ADU detection task. An average run over four training epochs took less than 30 minutes to train. The next section targets the experiments' implementation.

3.7.2 Implementation

The Hugging Face Transformers' library [102] makes it possible to access each LM in a uniform way and use the same code scaffolding when executing the ADU detection task. We use Hugging Face Transformers v. 4.1.1 with a simpletransformers wrapper v. 0.51.9 for the integration of tuning visualization. The Python version the experiments are run on is 3.6.12 and the PyTorch handling the ML in the background is of version 1.7.0.

The experiments are divided into three simple steps: initialization, training and evaluation. Table 3.5 summarizes the experimental setup. Three language groups, "German", "French" and their combination "Bilingual" are represented by five LMs. Defined by the group is the dataset to be applied. To each LM, there is a corresponding model type. An experiment is the run-through of one LM. For each experiment,

Group	Input dataset	Language Model	Model type
German	german_adu_set	bert-base-german-cased	bert
	german_adu_set	distilbert-base-german-cased	distilbert
French	french_adu_set	camembert-base	camembert
Bilingual	bilingual_adu_set	bert-base-multilingual-cased	bert
	bilingual_adu_set	distilbert-base-multilingual-cased	distilbert

Table 3.5: Experimental setup: languages, datasets, models and types.

the two variables `"bert_type"` and `"bert_name"` are set as keys in a dictionary and then handed to the `ClassificationModel`'s constructor.

ClassificationModel. The ADU detection task is a multiclass classification task, meaning each sentence has to be classified to exactly one out of three labels, distinguishing it from binary classification tasks, where two labels are given and from multilabel classification tasks, where one sequence can also be classified into several classes at once. Therefore, a `ClassificationModel` is the architecture of choice. The values for `"bert_type"` used in this experiment are: `"bert"`, `"camembert"` and `"distilbert"`. They correspond to a JSON config file from transformers, which contains the preconfiguration as used in the author's papers. This preconfiguration is limited to the used architecture and parameters but does not include the concrete weights of a model. The default arguments set by the model type can easily be overwritten using the `"args"` parameter. The five LMs share three model types: German BERT and multilingual BERT are both `"bert"` architectures and have a dedicated, optimized `"distilbert"` version available whereas CamemBERT has its own type. The `"bert_name"` determines which pretrained PyTorch model will be loaded from a checkpoint later in training using the method `"from_pretrained()"`. The names are mapped to a model-task-variant such as `BertForSequenceClassification`, which comprises a BERT encoder stack with saved weights and an additional task-specific final layer ("*sequence classification head*") with an output size of the passed `"num_labels"`. Even so depending on the `"bert_name"` is the corresponding tokenizer class, which is the `BertTokenizer` based on `WordPiece` for bert models, `SentencePiece` for CamemBERT and the `DistilBertTokenizer` for DistilBERT, which is equivalent to the `BertTokenizer`.

Train method. Subsequently, the `"train_model()"` method initiates the overall training process. It receives a pandas `DataFrame` of the respective language containing 90% of the data volume. At first, the model object and its associated tokenizer are downloaded from the Hugging Face model hub¹⁹ and cached. The pretrained model is identified and instantiated with its weights. The tokenizer receives information according to its model whether the data have to be lower-cased, which is only the case for CamemBERT as the French model has no further use for casing as only the first tokens of each sentence are cased in French. Then, the input sentences are split according to the tokenizer's strategy. To the lists of tokens, special tokens representing the start and end of the sentence are added. Further, the tokenizer recalls the vocabulary associated with its model, which is then used as a token-to-ID map to convert the tokens to tensors of floats, the model's desired input format. As mentioned in the foundations 2.3.4, a positional encoding is added, to include word order. In the present case, a simple index depending on maximum sequence length is applied instead of cosine. The tensor obtained in this manner is then passed to the LM and the contained sentences are classified according to the three labels. The labels are used as the target for the loss function of the experiments, which is cross entropy. The actual training over four epochs is handled by a separate, internal `"train()"` method using PyTorch.

¹⁹Transformers model hub. Last retrieved 02.01.2021 from <https://huggingface.co/models>

Test method. The tuned models are then tested by the `eval_model()` method. The evaluation dataset is given to the model as a pandas Dataframe and contains the remaining 10% of the original subcorpus. Furthermore, the evaluation method receives some sklearn metrics [65] to be logged, an F1-score, averaged by the arithmetic mean over the three labels and the model's accuracy. The output is a 3-tuple formed by the result, which is a dictionary containing the evaluation results, a list of model outputs and a list of examples that achieved faulty predictions. The saved evaluation output along with the training output containing models, configs and vocabulary are handed in with this thesis.

3.7.3 Language Model Parameters

In the following, a brief explanation of the configuration options controlling the training and evaluation process of the experiments is presented. The majority of the arguments handed over to the model as a python dictionary 3.17 are chosen to be the same for each LM for better reproducibility except for the *learning rate*, which are individually optimized in the next subchapter. Overall, the parameters control every step of the experiments' conduction including tokenization, training, evaluation as well as file handling and logging.²⁰

```
bert_args={
  "reprocess_input_data": True,
  "overwrite_output_dir": True,
  "num_train_epochs": 4,
  'learning_rate': 1e-5,
  "output_dir": pathToDir + outputPath,
  "best_model_dir": pathToDir + outputPath + 'best/',
  'wandb_project': "berts_and_bees",
  "fp16": True,
  "manual_seed": 42,
  "wandb_kwarg":{
    "name": bert_name + '_OPTIMUM',
    "group": lang,
    "dir": pathToDir + outputPath,
  }
}
```

Figure 3.17: Language model parameters.

The data preparation is configured as follows: The automated lowercasing of the tokens is disabled for four of the LMs are cased and CamemBERT can also handle case-sensitive input. The default encoding to be used is UTF-8. As UTF-8 has no issues with German or French symbols it is a decent choice. The maximum sequence length is selected according to related work [90] with a value of 128 tokens. When converting the tokens into features, the CPU is allowed to use multiprocessing.

²⁰Configuring a simpletransformers model. Last retrieved 02.02.2021 from <https://simpletransformers.ai/docs/usage/>

Since the tuning is highly dependent on its input configurations, there are numerous parameters to consider. The first ones are dedicated to computation. With the `"use_cuda"` parameter set to true, the computations are largely accelerated by the GPU. One of the great advantages of the Transformer is its parallelization, which is synergized by the GPU's architecture. As for the home computer constraint, the `"n_gpu"` parameter, defining the number of GPUs used to perform the matrix calculations are set to one. The `"fp16"` attribute, here set on true, regulates the usage of mixed-precision training. Mixed precision training is a speed boost implemented since the Pascal architecture of NVIDIA, which requires less memory, leading to faster calculation, and less memory bandwidth, leading to faster data transfer ²¹. *"Mixed"* precision refers to the models being converted to use 16-bit floats wherever applicable for example for the forward-pass or the gradient calculation, yet to keep 32-bit float weights to not lose task-specific precision, for example for calculation of the loss function or the multiplication with the `"learning rate"`. To prevent gradients from vanishing, loss scaling is used to preserve small gradient values. The gradient is cut once it reaches a predefined maximum `"maximum_gradient_clipping"`, here set to one, to assure it stays in a range, in which no overflows or underflows occur. The next parameter, `"gradient_accumulation_steps"` is set to one, meaning that after each training step, an optimization step is executed, saving memory at the cost of training time. After manually trying out different `"num_train_epochs"`, four epochs delivered the best results. Batchsize, defining the number of training samples per training step, is set to eight. The batchsize together with the `"learning rate"` determine a major part of the training efficiency. The `"learning rate"` determines the scale at which weights are updated towards the negative gradient. A common problem is the instability of the first, general layers due to a too high `"learning rate"` in early training steps during fine-tuning. An alternative solution to this problem except for freezing is the usage of a `"learning rate warm-up"` heuristic [32], which is tuned by its own parameter, here set to 0.06. To guarantee reproducible results the `"manual_seed"` picked is 42. The optimizer used in the experiments is the stochastic-gradient-descent-extension Adam [48], with its default epsilon of 1e-8.

Regarding evaluation, the `"eval_batch_size"` is set to eight, similar to the training batch size. Furthermore, there are some parameters for file handling such as `"cache_dir"`, indicating where model and tokenizer are cached, `"best_model_dir"` as the directory where the best model is saved after optimization, `"output_dir"`, where the results are saved and `"overwrite_output_dir"`, indicating whether saved models can be overwritten. `"reprocess_input_data"` regulates that the models are newly loaded, even when already available in `"cache_dir"`. Finally, two logging parameters are activated. `"wandb_project"` links the run to the weights and biases [6] project and `"wandb_kwarg"` hands some further key arguments to the project. The Optimization process as well and its logging are shown in the next subchapter.

3.7.4 Adam Optimization using W&B Sweeps

To further adjust the LMs to their datasets, they are trained with different settings. Optimization was conducted using the weights and biases framework [6]. Note that the term optimization is not used carefully, since the tuning steps aim at the improvement of the fit between the LMs and the ADU corpora, yet the tuning efforts

²¹Mixed precision training. Last retrieved 02.02.2021 from <https://docs.nvidia.com/deeplearning/performance/mixed-precision-training/index.html>

will lead to the mere identification of local optima and the focus of the experiments is to gain an objective overview on the LMs' performance and not to achieve mathematically perfect results. However, in the weights and biases framework, a set of runs using one LM under differently set parameters is called a "sweep". A sweep can be seen as the description of an optimization task. It contains the reference to the model to be optimized, a targeted metric, the model is about to be improved for and a search strategy for how to reach this goal. The sweep configuration as used for mBERT is depicted in Figure 3.18. Due to time restrictions, a simple, yet practical setup was chosen.

```
sweep_config = {
  'name': bert["bert_name"],
  'method': 'grid',
  'metric': {
    'name': 'accuracy',
    'goal': 'maximize'
  },
  'parameters': {
    'learning_rate': {
      'values': [9e-5, 8e-5, 7e-5, 6e-5, 5e-5, 4e-5, 3e-5, 2e-5, 1e-5]}]}
}
```

Figure 3.18: Sweep initialization.

The "sweep_config" receives the "bert_name" indicating the underlying LM's architecture and weights. The optimization method is a simple grid search over an array of learning rates. The parameters are optimized given a set metric. The goal of the optimization task is to maximize accuracy, hence the metric declared in the sweep is formulated accordingly. Accuracy is chosen over training loss to be focused on the final output and to gain independence from the optimizer. The optimizer as by default is Adam, a robust, adaptive learning rate optimizer, which is widely used [75]. Adam avoids oscillating around the local optimum, which occurs for standard stochastic gradient descent, in case the parameters heavily vary in their frequency by reinforcing the gradient using momentum and optimizing each weight by itself [48]. The input parameters are described in the following.

3.7.5 Optimizing Learning Rates

The learning rate determines the step size of the gradient descent algorithm, or in different terms it determines the amount at which the weights are updated. Having tried out several configurations, it turned out that learning rate and accuracy are correlated the most. As the tuning steps had the practical motivation to increase the LMs' performance without taking days of runtime, the choice for only one optimization parameter was made. Therefore, the learning rate is optimized over the array of values ($1 \cdot 10^{-5}$, $3 \cdot 10^{-5}$, $5 \cdot 10^{-5}$, $7 \cdot 10^{-5}$, $9 \cdot 10^{-5}$). If the best result happens to occur at the edge of the value range, further values were tested in following sweeps until the outer value is not the highest in the row. In descending order, the values ($1 \cdot 10^{-6}$, $3 \cdot 10^{-6}$, $5 \cdot 10^{-6}$, $7 \cdot 10^{-6}$, $9 \cdot 10^{-6}$) are run. Notice that the intervals have to be decreased in order not to reach zero. Subsequently, the impacts of learning rates on accuracy are visualized.

Figure 3.19: Tuning results of bert-base-german-cased.

Figure 3.19 shows the impact of different learning rates on the German BERT model in a diagram. The x-coordinates of the data points correspond to the learning rates, whereas the y-coordinates correspond to the achieved accuracy of each run. For German BERT, the lower limit of learning rates scored highest in accuracy, therefore the step-wise decrease of the learning rate was executed with the highest accuracy for a value of $7 \cdot 10^{-6}$.

Figure 3.20: Tuning results of distilbert-base-german-cased.

The next tuning sweep portrayed is the one of the German DistilBERT model. For DistilBERT the best learning rate is $1 \cdot 10^{-5}$, which delivers the strongest run in the sweep, confirmed by three additional runs. The tuning of German Distilbert can be seen in Figure 3.20.

Figure 3.21: Tuning results of camembert-base.

Regarding the French CamemBERT, the runs with the learning rates of $1 \cdot 10^{-5}$ and $7 \cdot 10^{-5}$ are competitive. As the former is positioned at the edge of the value range, a follow-up run needs to be executed, followed by another run due to a new-found maximum. As a result, the strongest learning rate lies at $9 \cdot 10^{-6}$. The tuning results of the French LM can be found in Figure 3.21.

Figure 3.22: Tuning results of bert-base-multilingual-cased.

For multilingual BERT, the learning rate of $1 \cdot 10^{-5}$ performs best. Strikingly, multilingual BERT has a poor run with the medium learning rate $5 \cdot 10^{-5}$. Figure 3.22 depicts all of mBert's runs.

Figure 3.23: Tuning results of distilbert-base-multilingual-cased.

Figure 3.23 shows the tuning results of the multilingual version of DistilBERT. The accuracy scores of the different learning rates are moderately decreasing, with a learning rate of $9 \cdot 10^{-6}$ leading to the best overall score. It is noticeable that every LM needed some extension by values lower than $1 \cdot 10^{-5}$.

As a consequence of the tuning step, the following learning rates were chosen for the models. bert-base-german-cased performed best with a learning rate of $7 \cdot 10^{-6}$. distilbert-base-german-cased delivered its best accuracy under a learning rate of $1 \cdot 10^{-5}$. The best learning rate for camembert-base is $9 \cdot 10^{-6}$. multilingual BERT trains most effectively exploiting a learning rate of $1 \cdot 10^{-5}$ and the multilingual distilbert's learning rate of choice is $9 \cdot 10^{-6}$. Each of the LMs' best configurations was subsequently initialized, trained and tested on the ADU detection datasets. Their results are evaluated in the coming chapter.

4. Evaluation

Following the contextual understanding, data understanding, data preparation and the modeling of the experiments, finally, the results are evaluated. The evaluation chapter is subdivided into three subchapters. Subchapter 4.1 observes the four measured metrics macro- and micro-averaged F-measure, MCC and evaluation loss. Thereafter, subchapter 4.2 analyses the errors on label-level using confusion matrices and a ROC curve. At last, the base is given to evaluate the hypotheses 4.4 formulated in chapter 1.2.

4.1 F-measure, MCC and Evaluation Loss

The logged measures printed out in the result files are macro F-measure, micro F-measure, MCC and evaluation loss. After defining the metrics, the scores achieved by each LM are investigated and compared. The results can be found in Table 4.1.

F-measure, also called F1-score, is a weighted harmonic mean over the metrics precision and recall [78]. Precision represents the share of the correctly identified number of a label in relation to the sum of test entries predicted to wear this label. For instance, the share of "*non-argumentative*" sentences that really are "*non-argumentative*" as compared to the total number of entries the model classifies as "*non-argumentative*". Recall is the share of correct predictions in relation to all predictions of a label, for example the percentage of predicted "*non-argumentative*" labels per total of "*non-argumentative*" examples. Recall R and precision P are aggregated through the following formula in Python's sklearn library ²²:

$$F_1 = 2 \frac{P \cdot R}{P + R} \quad (4.1)$$

As the experiments involve a set of labels with the cardinality three, the metric has to be averaged over the classes' distribution, which can be done in several ways. If the average is constructed as an arithmetic mean over the single-label F-measures at large, the multiclass F-measure is "*macro-averaged*". If the average is computed for each label's precision and Recall, the multiclass F-measure is "*micro-averaged*". The micro-averaged F-measure is synonym to the LM's accuracy used as the maximization goal for tuning. Both F-measures are included in the evaluation. Find the resulting formulae for macro and micro F-measure using three classes l below.

²²F1 in sklearn. Last retrieved 02.04.2021 from https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.metrics.f1_score.html

$$microF_1 = \frac{2 \sum_{l=1}^3 P_l \sum_{l=1}^3 R_l}{\sum_{l=1}^3 P_l + R_l} \quad (4.2)$$

$$macroF_1 = \frac{\sum_{l=1}^3 F_{1l}}{3} \quad (4.3)$$

MCC. The next metric to be evaluated is the Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC). As a correlation metric it can take values close to one for a positive correlation, close to zero for chance correlation and close to -1 for negative correlation. MCC takes different class distributions into account, which is useful in the present case since premises are most frequent in the adu datasets followed by *noadu* labels, followed by claims. The MCC calculation using three labels looks as follows.

$$MCC = \frac{c \cdot s - \sum_{l=1}^3 p_l - t_l}{\sqrt{(s^2 - \sum_{l=1}^3 p_l^2) \cdot (s^2 - \sum_{l=1}^3 t_l^2)}} \quad (4.4)$$

Thereby, l is the number of labels, t_l is the number of times the label truly occurs, p_l is the number of times the label is predicted, c is the number of correct predictions and s is the total sample size.

Evaluation loss. The third metric to be evaluated is evaluation loss. As the loss function that has already been used for training can be applied to the evaluation set as well, it is easily logged. Other than F-measure and MCC, it is targeted on the deviation between prediction and true labels. Measuring the error instead of the quality, the metric has to be minimized. The evaluation loss presently measured is cross-entropy loss, where a negative sum over a predicted distribution $p(x)$ and a logarithmically compressed true distribution $q(x)$ is made.

$$Loss(p, q) = - \sum p(x) \log(q(x)) \quad (4.5)$$

The four metrics were measured on the bilingual adu test sets. The results for each LM are summarized in Table 4.1. The performance values for the LMs are rounded up to four decimal places. In the German group, bert-base-german-cased performed best. The LM overall achieved substantial results on the ADU detection task with the highest $macroF_1$ -score of 0.5805, the highest $microF_1$ of 0.6184 and the highest MCC score 0.3737. The evaluation loss of the German LM is appropriately low with a value of 0.9321. Performing minimally worse is distilbert-base-german-cased. With a macro F-measure of 0.5342, an accuracy of 0.5931 and a MCC of 0.3305, the German DistilBERT stays behind the heavy-weight BERT. As for the loss, distilbert achieves a slightly lower value (0.9074) than German BERT. For the French LMs, camembert-base is the only representative. Its F-measures are with a value of 0.5300 for $macroF_1$ and a value of 0.6005 for $microF_1$ under the lowest achieved in the experiments, the same is valid for the frequency-corrected MCC with a value of 0.3177. Although camembert-base is situated in the backfield of the LMs, its misclassification values and MCC are still above chance correlation. Surprisingly, the evaluation loss of camembert-base is the lowest with 0.9074. Differences between loss results and F1 and MCC could be explained via outlier features, influencing the

loss function as a distance measure but having no impact on the misclassification metrics. In the group of the multilingual LMs, bert-base-multilingual-cased has a $macroF_1$ of 0.5734 and a $microF_1$ of 0.6164 and an MCC of 0.3691, slightly less than the best-performing German BERT. The value of its evaluation loss is with 1.0363 the highest in the experiments. Finally, distilbert-base-multilingual-cased performs mediocre across the metrics having a $macroF_1$ of 0.54434, a $microF_1$ of 0.6037, a MCC of 0.3353 and an evaluation loss of 0.9156.

		macro F1	micro F1	MCC	Loss
<i>German</i>	German BERT	0.5801	0.6184	0.3737	0.9321
	German DistilBERT	0.5342	0.5931	0.3305	0.9074
<i>French</i>	CamemBERT	0.5300	0.6005	0.3177	0.9017
<i>Multilingual</i>	mBERT	0.5734	0.6164	0.3691	1.0363
	mDistilBERT	0.5443	0.6037	0.3353	0.9156

Table 4.1: Summary of the results.

Overall, the LMs perform the ADU detection task with moderate success. Concerning the F-measures and MCC the models perform within a close range of 5-6%. For macro F1, German BERT ranks first, followed by mBERT, then mDistilBERT, German DistilBERT and CamemBERT. It is noteworthy, that four out of the five compared models fit in the performance difference between two versions of one model. For MCC the ranking is identical, therefore the picture is homogenous. All of the MCC values demonstrate a positive, yet not perfect correlation of predictions and actual classes, which are further analysed on label-level in the following chapter. According to the micro F1-score, the ranking stays the same except for CamemBERT and German DistilBERT switching places. Every LMs micro F1 outperforms every other LMs macro F1. The reason behind this relation probably lies in the high occurrence of the premise label, positively influencing the micro F1 score while negatively influencing the macro F1. Therefore, MCC is considered the most meaningful metric in this evaluation. LMs ranking best for evaluation loss, rank the worst in terms of the other metrics, weakening the evaluation loss’s interpretability. In general, the LMs stay behind the agreement of the human gold standard (Cohen’s κ of 0.79) from chapter 3.4.5, leaving some room for improvement. The evaluation is continued in the following subchapter, analyzing each LM’s confusion matrix and an overall ROC curve to finer quantify the error.

4.2 Confusion Matrices and ROC Curve

To further understand the metrics measured in the previous section, the models’ classification results are analyzed on the label level. Therefore, every LM’s confusion matrix is examined for trends and peculiarities, that can not be seen in the aggregated metrics.

Figure 4.1: Confusion matrix of bert-base-german-cased.

All LMs face a set of similar issues regarding their classification errors. These are illustrated in the following by the example of German BERT. The test set used for German BERT is the 10% split of the German ADU subcorpus, containing 151 non-argumentative entries with the label 0, 79 claims with the label 1 and 205 premises with the label 2. It is useful to know, how well this set of real labels is predicted by the models, a notion expressed by the recall measure. Figure 4.1 portrays the results of German BERT in detail. The per-label precision can be computed by sharing the number of a correctly classified label on the diagonal through the sum of the row. Likewise, the per-label recall can be computed by sharing the number of a correctly classified label on the diagonal through the sum of the column. For label 0, the non-argumentatives, the correct classification is found more frequently (84) than the wrong classifications. Misclassifying a non-argumentative sentence as a premise (54) happens more frequently than misclassifying it as a claim (13). Since the misclassifications are rather frequent, the recall of label 0 equals 0.66, a mediocre value. Label 1, the claims, is correctly classified 32 times by German BERT. More test examples are predicted to be premises (41) than to be actual claims (32), which can be seen as a poor result. However, misclassifying a claim as non-argumentative is very rare (6). Due to the weak disambiguation of false premises, label 1 achieves a weak recall value of 0.41. As label 2, the premises, is the most frequent label in the dataset, it shows itself the easiest to predict. A total of 153 true premises is identified correctly. The most common misclassification of premises (38) is the wrong prediction as non-argumentative, an issue that also appeared in the annotations as identifying the edge of an argument can be challenging. In 14 cases, a premise was wrongly suspected to be a claim.

The pattern, here seen in the case of German BERT, repeats itself throughout the results of the LMs. The correctly-classified non-argumentatives are moderately high, while more likely to be confused with a premise than with a claim. Claims are unlikely to be identified at all as they are more frequently held for a premise, yet claims are not confused with non-argumentatives. The prediction of premises is beneficial, achieving recall values above 0.7, and if they are confused, they are labeled as non-argumentative.

Figure 4.2: Confusion matrix of distilbert-base-german-cased.

Following the trends identified for German BERT, the German DistilBERT only varies in absolute numbers. Label 0 is correctly classified in 90 cases, six times more than for German BERT. Label 1’s correct predictions sum up to 22, ten less than those of German BERT. Label 3 is correctly identified 146 times, seven less than the other German LM. The misclassification of claims is even worse than for German BERT, shown by the recall of 0.28. The exact numbers can be found in Figure 4.2.

Figure 4.3: Confusion matrix of camembert-base.

CamemBERT struggles similar to the German models. The label allocation drawn in the French test set is slightly different, label 0 is represented 136 times, label 1 is represented 70 times and label 2 227 times. As a consequence, the correctly classified label 0 of 82 for CamemBERT is competitive with the German models, corresponding to 91 recognized non-argumentatives in the other data set. The label misclassification of claims as premises is very strong for CamemBERT with a claim recall of 0.27. Note that when computing an F1-score, this misclassification influences not only the recall of the claim label, but also inhibits the precision of the premise’s precision, an effect from which CamemBERT suffered in particular. CamemBERT’s confusion matrix is shown in Figure 4.3.

Figure 4.4: Confusion matrix of bert-base-multilingual-cased.

A positive exception can be found in mBERT’s confusion matrix, see Figure 4.4. The bilingual test set comprises 286 non-argumentative sentences, 153 claims and 429 premises. The multilingual BERT correctly classifies 174 non-argumentatives with more missclassifications as premise than as claim, but the claim label deviates from the other models. mBERT correctly classifies 61 claims and mistakenly classifies 67 claims as premises. The classification error is still higher than the correct classification but the share of true claims is far higher than for the monolingual LMs. This positive pattern could be explained due to the usage of multilingual pretraining, which gives the LM an enhanced insight into the formulations of claims. Since 25 claims are predicted as false label 0, the claim recall of mBERT is moderate with a value of 0.40. The premise recall of mBERT is 0.7.

Figure 4.5: Confusion matrix of distilbert-base-multilingual-cased.

The last confusion matrix depicted belongs to multilingual DistilBERT, see Figure 4.5. The errors of mDistilBERT follow the same patterns as the other LMs. Label 0 is correctly identified 160 times, 14 less than mBERT. Label 1 is classified less reliably than by mBERT with 47 correct classifications and a claim recall of 0.31. The expected superior knowledge on claims of mBERT is not exploited by mDistilBERT. On the other hand, 317 premises are correctly classified, leading to a premise recall of 0.74.

Figure 4.6 summarizes the results of all confusion matrices in one Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) curve, measuring the models' capability to separate between labels ²³. On the x-axis, one finds the true positive rate, which equals each label's recall. On the y-axis, one finds the false positive rate measuring the share of other classes that are incorrectly predicted as the respective class. The ROC curve depicts the relation true and false prediction of a class with respect to the label allocation. The plots per language-label pair of all LMs are close to each other. While a perfect ROC curve with a maximum area under the curve is not reached, (compare to the confusion matrices filled with values apart from the diagonals), the predictions are more than chance-correlated. Not surprisingly, the overall claim classification is characterized by low ROC values. Another negative outlier is CamemBERT's premise classification. Other than that, German BERT's and mBERT's premises have a convex ROC curve.

Figure 4.6: ROC curve of the experiments.

All the scrutinized LMs show similar regularities in their classification errors. Positive to report are the low confusion of non-argumentative sentences and claims, where the models seem to catch a difference, as well as the good recall of premises. Although premises are also the most likely label, they show a decent true-positive rate to false-positive rate ratio, excluding the possibility of premises only being predicted due to their frequency. mBERT manages to handle the misclassification of claims more reliably than the other LMs, which could be caused by its bilingual pre-training. To conclude, the LMs perform above chance but under the human baseline. Potential reasons behind these findings are investigated in an error analysis.

²³ROC curve. Last retrieved 02.04.2021 from <https://towardsdatascience.com/understanding-auc-roc-curve-68b2303cc9c5>

4.3 Error Analysis

Due to the results' moderate quality, an error analysis is conducted to identify potential reasons for the model's difficulties. Four areas are pinpointed for explanation, namely task difficulty, gap between annotation and classification task, computational capacities and the amount of data.

The first reason why the LMs are not performing perfectly on the ADU detection task experiments is the task's difficulty. The assignment of sentences to claims and premises and non-argumentative labels has not one true answer, such as for instance the assignment of a word to its word class such as noun or adjective. The degree of ambiguity increases with the number of difficult cases. Staying with the word class example, there are just few examples where the answer is not clear, such as the expression "*to race*". However, there are plenty of difficult cases in argument identification as for example implicit and controversial claims and premises, the identification of opinionated sentences, the presence or absence of ADU indicators and many more enumerated and explained in chapter 3.4.4. As the original corpus was not designed with this task in mind, speakers were not instructed to use predefined argument structures as in the majority of other corpora. Keeping Europarl's non-argumentative sentences might enhance the degree of reality, yet it includes the entire segmentation problem, leading to misclassifications of premises and non-argumentative labels.

In order to cope with these ambiguities, various assumptions were made for the annotation task, resulting in a solid agreement measure. The reached agreement is almost entirely based on guidelines and communication, two factors that the LMs have no access to. The assumption that ADUs have to be on sentence level is a simplification, leading to ambiguity for the LMs. In addition, even the human gold standard does not entirely agree. As the task is no image classification with an obvious answer for human experts, the labels are no absolute truth. Equipped with working definitions, a clear workflow, indicator words and decision rules for the sentence-level, the Intra-annotator-agreement of one person alone is at 93%. Therefore, a final subjectivity of the task remains.

Furthermore, the computational resources for the experiments were limited. The experiments were conducted on a student pc using a single GPU, whose storage is easily filled up. This limitation makes it impossible to execute an exhaustive search for parameters using a suitable search strategy without spending a disproportional amount of time. For the same reason, potential higher-performant LMs were upfront excluded from the experiments. Despite these considerations, it is not very probable that more capacities would have enhanced the classification quality by a tremendous amount since all the models examined deliver similar results.

Another potential source of error could be the ADU detection corpus's size. A larger amount of training data is beneficial for the task. The datasets used for related work have more training examples for the models to tune. The German and French datasets only have a volume of 4342 and 4328 entries, which is rather small when considering the difficulty of the task. Although the bilingual dataset is larger with its 8670 entries, the multilingual models do not outperform the others. Nonetheless, the subcorpus size was as well determined by the amount of time available for label creation.

4.4 Hypothesis Evaluation

Subsequent to the quantitative evaluation of the metrics and qualitative critical analysis of room for improvement, the evaluation of the hypotheses is presented. In chapter 1.2, three hypotheses on bilingual LM performance were formulated, which can finally be answered.

H1: There is a performance difference between German and French LMs.

H1 can be accepted. The German BERT model outperforms the French CamemBERT model on macroF1, microF1 and MCC. For the German DistilBERT, the results are not as clear as the model outperforms CamemBERT on macroF1 and MCC, yet the French model shows a superior micro F1 score. Since there is currently no distilled version of CamemBERT available to directly compare the model to, CamemBERT results are measured against the German BERT only. According to the fact that model performance on directly translated corpora varies dependent of the input language, there is reason for further research to investigate the issue.

H2: There is a performance difference between monolingually and multilingually pretrained LMs.

H2 is not decidable based on the available data. On the four scrutinized metrics the rankings of the LMs are as follows. The ranking for macroF1 and MCC follows the pattern German BERT > mBERT > mDistilBERT > German DistilBERT > CamemBERT. Translated to monolingual and multilingual LMs the ranking looks like monolingual > multilingual > multilingual > monolingual > monolingual. Since the multilingual LMs are ranked in the middle across all metrics, they perform neither better nor worse than the monolingual models. Although the multilingual models are finetuned on the doubled volume of the monolingual models, they do not achieve higher scores. However, mBERT shows the smallest error in the classification of claims as premises, which could be explained by its bilingual pretraining. The error rate alone is not enough justification to confirm the hypothesis though, hence, the question remains open.

H3: German and French LMs perform worse than English LMs from the literature.

H3 is confirmed. The English state of the art in argument identification is set by [100], reporting a macroF1 score of 93.1% on AraucariaDB, of 85.19% for student essays, 84.15% for web discourse and 74.86% for blog comments. None of the tested French, German and multilingual models reaches the English state of the art. Nevertheless, the tasks are not entirely comparable since the corporas' argument structures are given by default and are therefore less realistic. On the contrary, the comparison should give a motivating baseline to further close the gap produced by the English research focus.

To conclude, H1 and H3 can be confirmed, while H2 calls for further research. After the evaluation of the research questions, the findings are deployed for discussion and outlook.

5. Discussion and Outlook

Finally, the insights of the work are discussed. This includes the review of potentials and limitations of cross-lingual AM systems as identified through this work. The proceedings are reflected in section “*lessons learned*” and an outlook on future projects that could follow this thesis is given.

5.1 Potentials of Cross-lingual AM Systems

The need for cross-lingual AM systems was ignored for a long time. This is not based on reason, since the benefits from automated argument analysis and related applications are not only interesting for the English language. To close this gap, which is known as language divide in NLP, very recently, cross-lingual AM endeavors were started, mostly focusing on the translation of annotated corpora. Due to the practice of transfer learning, pretrained LMs that already capture some notion on their respective set of languages are freely available to be tuned on any NLP task, including AM.

A major insight is that languages profit from one another. In the experiments, we found that the bilingually pretrained mBERT dealt better with the problem to correctly identify claims. The other LMs scrutinized often misclassified claims as premises. It is assumed, that this enhanced classification results derive from mBERT’s bilingual pretraining. During the annotation process, it helped in difficult cases to consult the other language’s version of the speech. Sometimes, a claim that was neutrally expressed as a statement in language a , was argumentatively expressed in the translation, for instance containing a claim indicator such as “*therefore*”. Having the same text passage formulated in two languages, made the argument less ambiguous. Thus, the sum of the whole syntactical information of two translated sentences seems to be higher than the sum of its parts. This matches the typological features of French and German such as word order and suffixes, complementing each other. Due to this observation, the work on real-world, human-translated data seems more meaningful than comparable work on machine translations. It is possible that pure label projection as done in related work, leads to an information loss. This intuition is supported by the results of Toledo-Ronen [90]. They found that an mBERT model when pretrained on a set of related languages, for instance Germanic languages, performed better on evidence detection and stance detection. Further, the pretraining effectiveness depends on task complexity and agreement. As already identified in the error analysis, the ADU-detection task on real-world speeches counts as a difficult task. Building on these findings, it could be interesting to assess for which tasks in the AM pipeline combined or single-language pretraining works most effectively. In this scope a comparison between a segmentation task, an ADU function prediction, a relation prediction and a quality prediction could be of

interest. Further thoughts on future lines of work are summarized in chapter 5.4. It remains to be noted that the combination of different source languages, adding information, and subjective AM tasks, requiring information, could be a potential. Furthermore, the democratization of several languages for AM, use cases in national and international contexts and the tapping of new data sources could enhance AM on the cross-lingual scale.

5.2 Limitations of Cross-lingual AM Systems

Identified potentials are always accompanied by limitations, some of which are mentioned in the following. First of all, this thesis is not capable to make statements on the argumentation style of the languages. In general, it is considered beneficial that the source languages contained in the Europarl corpus are not further chosen. This results in an abundance of source languages, with French and German incorporating both roles, the role of source language and as target language. Therefore, there is not one language defining the grammatical structure of the target language. Instead, both languages are treated equally, some speeches are originally French, others are originally German, again others are originally spoken in a different language. In case one might want to test, whether different native speakers argument in a different manner, a task called cross-lingual argument analysis, one had to design a different experiment. Due to the various linguistic origins of the Europarl speeches they deliver no further insights. Consequently, to measure argumentation styles of native speakers, one has to conduct experiments, in which the native texts are created from scratch. For instance, native speakers would have to write argumentative texts or have to discuss predefined topics in groups. Therefore, the lacking original creation of data is one limitation not covered in this work.

Another limitation of this thesis consists in the real-world origin of the corpus, leading to moderate results as compared to the English baseline. One could even go as far as to ask whether automated AM on real-world data is feasible. From the mediocre results achieved by the LMs, one might draw the following two conclusions. First, there is plenty of room for improvement, presented in the error analysis from chapter 4.3. Most of the improvements could not be executed due to the time restrictions of the master thesis. In the aftermath, with more time, more computational resources and follow-up experiments, one could continue to catch up with the English baseline. However, further research is desirable as the gap is not yet closed. Second, the task difficulty inherent to real-world argumentation explicitly shows that broader benchmarks are still challenging. Research is only useful if it is applicable and generalizable. The present bilingual datasets are taken from real minutes from the European parliament, including non-argumentative passages and complex argumentative strategies. These are typical data as one might need to support political scientists in real analyses. Once the benchmark results turn out well on highly pre-designed corpora, one can take the next step and venture into more realistic data. Particularly the fact that the results are not perfect shows that further effort is necessary.

5.3 Lessons Learned

In the lessons learned, some final thoughts that emerged considering the proceedings are discussed. As the largest share of time spent in an NLP thesis concerns preprocessing and the preprocessing had the peculiarity of dealing with two languages, the differences in handling German and French are scrutinized. On the cost side, the effort to preprocess German and French data is lower than expected. After the identification of search terms to reduce the corpus size, the search terms had to be translated to French. As some of the search terms included adjectives, one had to be aware that for the French regex search, male and female inflection of the adjective had to be considered. Additionally, when cleaning the XML files, one had to look up the different forms of address that are used in the parliament domain, which were language-specific and can contain abbreviations, yet are easy to find. Regarding the LMs, most of the language-specific knowledge was encapsulated in the models themselves, hence, no exhaustive preprocessing had to be taken care of. A difference between German and French LMs is their included tokenizer, which is based on WordPiece for German and on SentencePiece for French. Also, for the French LM CamemBERT, no case-sensitive version is provided. Other than that, a good takeaway when processing French data is always having the encoding set to UTF-8 to guarantee readability. On the performance side, multilingual pretraining gives the LMs the possibility to develop more general feature representations, which can be exploited for various NLP tasks.

Having included the human factor to the workflow, meaning that the corpus was neither machine-translated, nor were the annotations projected, one gains invaluable insights in the difficulties of ADU detection. As a consequence, the performance of the LMs is easier to interpret from a qualitative perspective and the resulting annotated corpus is a novel contribution for bilingual AM endeavors.

5.4 Future Work

Several lines of work could build on the bilingual ADU detection task. Two directions can be taken in the short and in the long term.

In the short term, the first idea that comes to mind is to try out some approaches to enhance the final results. This thought fits with the multidirectional connections in the applied CRISP-DM framework. Every insight can be deployed for continuous improvement. In the annotation phase, a substantial agreement could be reached although the task is indeed difficult. Then, the error analysis showed that an inherent problem for the LMs compared to the annotators is their lack of guidelines. The decision rules given to the annotators such as how to assign the "claim" label when there are several claim candidates are based on sentence order. For instance, if an annotator is not sure whether a sentence is a claim, he should check the logical inference chain by including a "therefore". Derived from this, one could hand the LM the information on sentence order by modeling the classification task as a sequence-pair classification task (see [20]). In the experiments' implementation, the LMs are only provided with the tokens within a sentence. Subsequently giving them a sentence pair as input data could mean a performance difference similar to the one between word embeddings and contextual word embeddings. The implementation of a sentence pair classification task could be an interesting short-term follow-up work.

Moreover, the tuning could be extended in future work. One reason behind the mediocre LM performance might lie in insufficient tuning data. A promising approach to solve this issue could be adding an additional pretraining task before the fine-tuning on the ADU detection. To limit the annotation effort, the corpus was artificially trimmed. Nevertheless, a huge volume of domain- and language specific data is available. The proposed solution is to use the entire Europarl corpus for an additional MLM task to further pretrain the LMs and give them a domain-specific register. The thereby created LMs could be called GermanEuroparlBERT or CamemEuroparlBERT and were perfectly prepared for the task.

In the long term, the enhanced LMs and the corpus could be exploited for further research. Since the ADU detection task is just the first step of the entire AM pipeline, it is possible to expand the pipeline by including the following steps. Building on this line of work, it is also an option to elaborate the simple claim-premise model toward a more advanced argumentation model, e.g., to annotate support and attack relations, which could be trivially implemented using the brat tool. Therefore, one just has to add a relation definition and then drag and drop lines between the marked sentences.

A further extension is the enclosing of further languages following the same methodology. In a similar manner as the Fishcheva [26] corpus extends the microtext corpus, this subcorpus could be extended by further languages that are already present in the Europarl corpus.

The last long-term extension concerns the LMs' prediction function. The trained and tuned LMs could be used to build a simple argument recognition tool for German and French. The user just copies a text into the application and the application returns the identified ADUs. A such small tool could be the start for further automated argument analysis in languages other than English.

6. Conclusion

To close the language divide widespread in NLP, a bilingual ADU detection task is conducted on French and German data. The bilingual data is drawn from the popular Europarl corpus, containing proceedings of the European Parliament between 1996 and 2011. At first, the volume of data to be annotated is significantly reduced based on semantic queries representing the controversial topic of “*nuclear energy*”. Then, nine previously trained human annotators identified the sentences as “*non-argumentative*”, “*claims*” or “*premises*” on the French and the German subcorpus. Taking this human gold standard as a baseline, the ADU detection experiments are conducted, comparing five state-of-the-art LMs regarding their macro and micro F1 score, their MCC and their evaluation loss. Two LMs, German BERT and German DistilBERT, are representing the German state of the art, one LM, CamemBERT, is representing the French state of the art and two LMs, mBERT and mDistilBERT, are representing the multilingual state of the art. All of the LMs performed under the human baseline, German BERT outperformed CamemBERT, showing that pretraining language influences the output, however, the LMs also stay behind the English baseline, showing that the gap opened by the language divide is not yet closed. It is discussed whether the multilingual pretraining could be a beneficial factor for LM performance, still, further research is necessary.

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Declaration

I declare that this thesis was composed by myself and that the work contained therein is my own, except where explicitly stated otherwise in the text.

Saarbrücken, February 9th 2021

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'F. G.' with a stylized flourish at the end.